

Deliverable report for

Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling

Project 101058632

Deliverable n°:	D6.3
Deliverable name:	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities
Version:	2.0
Release date:	30.11.2022
Dissemination level:	Public (PU)
Status:	Final
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Co-funded by
the European Union

Change Records

Version	Date	Changes	Edited by
v1.0	31.10.2022	Initial draft	Bruno Vicenzi
v2.0	30.11.2022	Adoption of the changes proposed by the reviewers	Bruno Vicenzi

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All WPs and Tasks

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2 ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan (for START)
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
ExCom	START's Executive Committee (WP leaders)
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KoM	Kick-off meeting
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
WP	Work Package
PM	Powder Metallurgy
TEG	ThermoElectric Generators
MTOD	Monitoring Tool for Online Dissemination
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

3 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present deliverable reports on the activity of WP6 “Dissemination and Communication” in the period 1st June 2022 - 30th November 2022¹ (M01-M06 of the START project).

It covers the endeavours within the following tasks (the only ones running in said period):

- Task 6.1: Specific project dissemination and communication tools
- Task 6.2: Technical and scientific dissemination
- Task 6.4: Clustering

During the period, 2 deliverables (D6.1 and D6.2) and a milestone (MS08) were achieved and reported. In fact, most of the tools necessary for the D&C activities have been developed, documented and submitted in the 2 mentioned deliverables, including:

- The Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP)
- The Project’s Graphical Identity (logo, branding).
- The START project website.
- A special area on the EPMA website devoted to the START project.
- Social Media platforms accounts (LinkedIn, YouTube, Twitter, Twitch, SlideShare)
- Leaflets, posters, banners
- The first issue of a public biannual newsletter
- 1 introductory video about the project

The partners already started dissemination at events, both in Europe (1st Scientific-Technical Conference of the Geological and Mining Institute of Spain, World PM2022, Madrid’s Science and Innovation Week, Raw Materials Week, II Extraordinary General Assembly of ASGMI) and in South America (CEPAL Regional Event, Perumin 2022, International Workshop in Geochemistry, EU-Latin America RM Convention, and EU-Latin America policy dialogue on the identification of Strategic and critical Raw Materials resources). Other events are being planned in early 2023.

Other disseminations included various Open-Source publications, and at least one article on a magazine is planned in early 2023.

The KPIs set for the D&C activities have been met (not considering those that have a longer deadline).

The clustering activity has begun in M03. Relative to the consortium, internal and external strategies for clustering have been developed. Exploiting the events attended, and with direct actions and contacts, especially with Europe-wide initiatives and institutions like the EIT KICs, a database of contacts is being developed.

¹ For practical reasons linked to text reviewing and submission, some details related to the last 2 weeks of November could not be reported and will be dealt with in the next deliverable of the same kind, D6.4 (M12).

4 INTRODUCTION: STRUCTURE OF WP6 AND GENERAL PLAN OF ACTIVITIES

4.1 OBJECTIVES OF WP6

The overall objective of WP6 is to disseminate widely the results of the START project in order to maximise its impact. The key objectives of this work package are:

- To raise awareness of all relevant parties (scientific and industrial communities, general public and policy makers) about START project activities in a coherent and consistent manner.
- To ensure an effective dissemination of the technical and scientific results of START project to the scientific and industrial communities.
- To ensure an effective communication of the achievements of START project to the wider scientific and technical communities, policy makers and the general public.
- To elaborate the Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) and update it when required.

Various communication activities are envisaged to disseminate the on-going and final project findings:

- Participations in congresses, workshops, webinars
- Training events
- Websites
- Scientific papers
- Newsletters and other publications
- Participation in trade fairs and exhibitions
- Other activities, etc.

EPMA, leading the WP, ensures a broad dissemination of the project progress and outcomes in Europe through its well-established network and website and its annual events and frequent Sectoral and Working Group meetings, even after the completion of the project. Nevertheless, all partners are required to collaborate in dissemination and communication by delivering content and executing some dissemination subtasks.

4.2 STRUCTURE OF WP6

4.2.1 Tasks

The activity is organised in 5 Tasks, whose scope and activities will be explained in the main chapters of this report.

- Task 6.1: Specific project dissemination and communication tools
- Task 6.2: Technical and scientific dissemination
- Task 6.3: Training activities
- Task 6.4: Clustering
- Task 6.5: Final event

The GANTT chart shows the start and end of each task. As can be seen, only Tasks 6.1, 6.2 and 6.4 have already begun, whereas task 6.3 is due to start in a few months and Task 6.5 only in Year 4, rather close to the end of the project.

Figure 1: GANTT chart for WP6. M01 = June 2022; M48 = May 2026.

4.2.2 Deliverables and Milestones

The WP contains a large number of deliverables, 15 out of a total of 39 for the whole project, but on the other hand only one milestone, that has already been achieved in M03 (August 2022).

The deliverables, also visible in Figure 2, can be grouped in the following categories:

- D6.1 - Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools (M02): This deliverable describes the project's website, addresses the inherent need of the project to develop the START graphical identity, together with all the other online tools designed to support objectives of WP6. *(Submitted and approved)*
- D6.2 - Dissemination and Communication Plan (M03): Document outlining the most efficient strategy and means for implementing the dissemination and communication activities. *(Submitted)*
- D6.3, D6.4, D6.6, D6.7, D6.9, D6.10, D6.12, D6.13 - Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities (M06, M12, M18, M24, M30, M36, M42, M48): Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed. *(D6.3 is the present report, D6.4 upcoming in 6 months)*
- D6.5, D6.8, D6.11, D6.14 - Training activities (M12, M24, M36, M48): Report on a 12-month basis describing the training activities implemented. *(D6.5 upcoming in 6 months)*
- D6.15 - Final Event (M46): Final event conference report.

5 TASK 6.1: SPECIFIC PROJECT DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION TOOLS

Task leader: EPMA; Participants: All; M01 to M48

The objective of this task is to develop tools and produce materials that will be used during and after the project to disseminate the information about the project, its partners, and its results. According to our proposal, these were the items that needed to be developed:

- The Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) at the start of the project and updated when required.
- The Project's Graphical Identity (logo, branding).
- The START project website.
- A special area on the EPMA website (www.epma.com) devoted to the START project.
- Social Media platforms, in particular:
 - A LinkedIn page for networking with the professional community (managed by EPMA).
 - A YouTube profile for engaging with the greater public (managed by EPMA).
 - A Twitter account for business and policy makers (managed by LPRC).
 - A Twitch profile for engagement with young people (managed by LPRC).
 - A SlideShare account for disseminating project presentations globally (managed by ASGMI).
- Leaflets, posters, banners, branded consumables that will be used as advertising material to be distributed in digital and/or physical versions.
- A public biannual newsletter to be distributed in digital and/or physical versions.
- A serious game (see WP7, Task 7.1 and deliverable D7.2)
- Videos about the project (2 generic videos, 1 at the start and one at the end, 3 more focused videos on specific topics).

The tools had been further described in the original proposal as in Table 1.

Table 1: Tools for Dissemination and Communication as indicated in the proposal.

Tool	Purpose	Audience	Due	Quantified target
Project Graphical Identity	A Graphical Identity for the START project (logo and general branding colour schemes, for the website, the social media, mail signatures for partners, and all other uses) will be developed in the first months.	All	M02	-
Project website	Main channel for information and major tool for the visibility of the START activities. Updated frequently, with a blend of status, push and active content, including: project overview; public documents; agenda; articles and news; multimedia. Individuals can also use the website to sign up to the newsletter and social media channels.	All groups	M02 onwards	Visitors: 2000 in year 1 rising to at least 4000 in year 4
Social media	LinkedIn, YouTube and Twitter will be considered as main dissemination channels, Slideshare and Twitch as secondary dissemination channels. LinkedIn supports community management with restricted fora. A YouTube channel will be used to engage with a broader audience by sharing videos, including an introduction to START, short interviews, and selected partner videos.	All groups	M02 onwards	Twitter: 1000 followers in year 1, rising to 2500 by the end of the project LinkedIn: 800 followers by the end of the project.
Videos	Some videos are planned for various uses: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A short generic video (0.5-1 min) with simple information, to be used for general awareness about START. • A mid-term longer video, highlighting preliminary project results. • 2 or more short videos focused on different subtopics within the project, with examples of improvements achieved within the project. • A short generic video (0.5-1 min) with simple information, to be used as a summary of the results obtained in START. 	Groups 1-4 1-3 2-3 1-4	M04 M24 M48 M48	Average of 200 views per video (at least 100 total views)
Newsletters	A public biannual newsletter will be circulated to individuals who sign up. The newsletter will include a summary of the activities over a 6-month period.	Groups 1-3	M06 onwards	Demand led but minimum of 500 per semester
Webinars/ seminars/ workshop	Communication of the project outcomes and activities, to share knowledge, ideas and updates.	Groups 2, 3	M06 onwards	Audience of 100 per event
Serious online game	A serious online game for capacity building on raw materials, sustainability and circular economy.	All groups	M24 onwards	Visitors: 300
Other publications	Articles on web-based innovation news services, like the Horizon Magazine, Cordis, and on commercial magazines like Open Access Management	All groups	M06 onwards	Total reach >400000

Many of these tools have already been developed, partially at least and anyway following the schedule and the details will be given in the next pages. Some interesting additions, like for instance the START comics, have been made to the original plans.

5.1 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN

The Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) has been already developed and reported in deliverable D6.2 (“Dissemination and Communication Plan”), submitted on 30th August 2022. The DCP, in its initial version, will lead the activity on Dissemination and Communication also in relationship with the other WPs, and will be updated during the project (at least twice during the project, at M24 and M48) to guarantee flexibility and optimisation of D&C efforts, as measured via the selected KPIs.

The DCP contains an outline of all the activities envisaged within the project for D&C, including the various procedures for publications, to monitor the performance of the D&C effort, etc.

It is a very comprehensive document that has been thoroughly described in D6.2: for this reason, we are not going to describe it again here in detail. For the sake of readability of this report, we will just list here the subchapters in which the DCP is divided.

1. Target audience segmentation
2. Events
3. Rules for Publication
 - 3.1. Deliverables
 - 3.2. General publications
 - 3.3. Publications on project website
 - 3.4. Publications on project's social media
 - 3.5. Publications on external media – magazines, journals, presentations in events
4. Project Graphical Identity
5. Project Website
6. Social Media
7. START Newsletter
8. Videos
9. Webinars / Seminars / Workshops
10. Scientific Publications and Participation to Scientific Events
11. Other Publications
12. Participation in Industrial Events
13. Participation in other Events
14. Materials for booths/physical distribution
 - 14.1. Leaflet(s)
 - 14.2. Roller banner(s)
 - 14.3. Poster(s)
 - 14.4. Consumables
15. Serious Online Game
16. START comics
17. Training
 - 17.1. START lectures during the EPMA PM Summer School
 - 17.2. ASGMI workshops
 - 17.3. Final Training Workshop
18. Clustering
19. Continuous Evaluation of D&C Performance
 - 19.1. KPIs
 - 19.2. WP6 meetings
 - 19.3. Continuous reporting on Funding & Tender website
20. Update of the DCP

The preparation of the DCP took several weeks in July/August 2022, and involved many of the partners, in particular those included in the project's ExCom. The text was collected by EPMA.

5.2 TARGET AUDIENCE SEGMENTATION

As written in the DCP, the audience for the project topics has been and will be segmented in 4 groups, depending on their role and possible interactivity with the project:

- **Group 1** - Policy makers and influencers concerned with the green transition and sustainable circular economy at European level. This group includes, local, regional, country and EU level political figures, especially those in charge and influential in all relevant policies concerning industry, minerals and mining, energy, supply chains, sustainability, and potentially all journalists, web- or print-based, all social media (LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube) influential people dealing with scientific, mining, resources, industrial, energy and sustainability topics.
- **Group 2** - Economically active entrepreneurs and industrial actors at European level in the three main segments of the value chain:
 - a. Raw material suppliers (mining sector)
 - b. TEG device producers (thermoelectric industry)
 - c. TEG utilisers (i.e., waste heat producers)
- **Group 3** - Scientific community across the geology, materials science, thermoelectric energy harvesting, renewable energy
- **Group 4** – General public across the EU

For maximum efficacy, the D&C activities will have to address each target groups with the correct approach (scientific/technical/non-technical/emotional, impact, economic features, and language tuned to the media).

In the first part of the project, D&C efforts have to use only limited material that is the basic project concept and some general information on the scientific and application background of the materials, technologies and devices that are of interest for the project. Therefore, Group 3 was hardly approachable, and only at a “superficial” level, as no foreground has yet been developed. On the other hand, most activities have been general (website, LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube), so potentially reaching all groups. Other activities in events were basically oriented towards group 2 or group 3 (but as explained with not very technical information).

5.3 PROJECT GRAPHICAL IDENTITY

The project's graphical identity has been already developed and reported in deliverable D6.1 (“Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools”), submitted on 29th July 2022. It must be used in all official project documents, including deliverables.

It includes:

- Colour branding
- Logo
- Fonts to be used in documents
- Templates
- A basic E-Mail signature

These items had to be prepared as early as possible to give everyone the correct instruments not only for dissemination but also for reporting. EPMA suggested the drafts of all items, which were evaluated by the ExCom and finally approved.

As this was a topic for a previous deliverable, we report here briefly only the items produced, that are visible in the figures below.

Figure 4: Basic colour composition for the START Project branding.

Figure 5: Final logo selected.

Figure 6: Graphic elements to be used while branding documents for the project.

Figure 7: Other graphic elements to be used while branding documents for the project.

Figure 8: START internal presentation template (July 2022, updated after selection of logo in the KoM).

Figure 9: START Word template (July 2022).

The START Project: <http://START-HEproject.com/>

Figure 10: Basic START E-Mail signature.

5.4 PROJECT WEBSITE

The project's website has been already developed and reported in deliverable D6.1 ("Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools"), submitted on 29th July 2022. It also constituted the criterion for the achievement of Milestone MS08 ("Project Website (M03) - Project website functional and accessible"), that was declared achieved on 22nd August 2022.

The website address is

www.START-HEproject.com

Another site address, www.HE-START.eu, is automatically redirected to the main address.

The website is continually updated in terms of contents and new features may be introduced (new pages, widgets, etc.) if deemed useful.

In fact, since the first development of the website, shown in the mentioned D6.1, some more documents and news have been published on it, and some modifications in the pages has been carried out.

The homepage has been modified (Figure 11) to include also, as an embedded item, the first introductory video (see chapter 5.10.1).

The screenshot shows the START project homepage. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for Home, The Project, Documents, News, Multimedia, Consortium, and CONTACT. Below the menu, the main heading reads "START project's primary objective is to build an innovation ecosystem in the European Union (EU) related to the development of sustainable and economically viable tellurium-free thermoelectric (TE) waste heat harvesting systems, to be applied in heavy industry, maritime industry and also as primary power source for off-grid sensors and IoT devices." Below this, there are three sections: "HOW TO ACHIEVE", "IMPACT OF START", and "START PROJECT ORGANISATION". A call to action says "Read more in the other website pages and subscribe to our newsletter and social media channels!". The main content area features a "START CONCEPT" diagram on the left and an embedded video on the right. The diagram illustrates a circular process: RECOVERY AND REUSE OF MINE WASTE (with a photo of a mine) leads to MATERIAL PROCESSING (with a photo of a factory), which leads to DEVICE (with a photo of a device), which leads to SCALE UP (with a photo of a large facility), which leads to VALIDATION (with a photo of a device), which leads back to RECOVERY AND REUSE OF MINE WASTE. The video on the right shows a cartoon character and text: "The thermoelectric materials will be sustainable, coming from EU-sourced ores and reclaimed wastes, depending on outside EU".

Figure 11: Detail of the START homepage as modified to include the new Introductory video (on the right side).

On the "Documents" page, there are now 7 documents for download (Figure 12):

- "Green energy harvesting"

- The initial A5 START flyer (see chapter 5.7.1)
- The English and Portuguese versions of the START factsheet provided by LNEG: “Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling”
- The presentation given by F. Neves (LNEG) at the event World PM2022 (see chapter 6.2.5)
- The presentation given by D. de Oliveira (LNEG) at the event EU-Latin America Convention on Raw Materials 2022 (see chapter 6.2.6)
- The Newsletter Issue #1 (see chapter 5.8.1).

More documents will be made available in the future.

Figure 12: Updated Documents page.

In the “News” page, the details of the participation to World PM2022 and the introduction to the Newsletter are now given (Figure 13, Figure 14, Figure 15).

In the “Multimedia” page, the introductory video is now embedded (Figure 16).

The “Contact” page (Figure 17) has been rearranged for more clarity.

Figure 13: The updated News page.

The screenshot shows a news article on the START website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'START' logo and links for Home, The Project, Documents, News, Multimedia, Consortium, and CONTACT. The main heading is 'START at World PM 2022 in Lyon (October 2022)', accompanied by a red lion logo. The article is titled 'The World PM2022 Congress & Exhibition organised by EPMA'. The text describes the 2022 World Congress and Exhibition on Powder Metallurgy, organized by EPMA, held in Lyon, France, from October 18-20, 2022. It mentions that the event is a major event for the powder metallurgy industry, with over 1000 exhibitors and 10000 attendees. The article also notes that START participated in the event, with several presentations and a booth. A 'Share this post' button is visible at the bottom of the article. At the very bottom of the page, there is a footer with the European Union logo and text: 'Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for errors.'

Figure 14: The News item about the participation to the World PM2022.

The screenshot shows a news article on the START website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the START logo and links for Home, The Project, Documents, News, Multimedia, Consortium, and CONTACT. The main heading of the article is "RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE Issue #1: our START Newsletter is here! (Nov 2022)". Below the heading is a sub-heading "BIANNUAL NEWSLETTER OF THE START PROJECT | ISSUE 1" and the START logo with "NEWSLETTER" underneath. A red banner contains the text "RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE for a Sustainable Future". The article title is "RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE: a newsletter that is not just a project's diary". The text of the article discusses the launch of the newsletter, its biannual schedule, and its focus on project progress, materials, processes, and sustainability. It includes a list of topics: "Critical minerals and raw materials sustainability in the EU" and "What is a thermoelectric material?". The article also mentions that the newsletter will provide updates on project activities, events, and dissemination topics, and that it is available for free download. A "Share This Post!" section with social media icons (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn) is located at the bottom of the article. At the very bottom, there is a footer with the European Union logo and text: "Co-Funded by the European Union. Co-Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them." and "© Copyright 2022 - 2022 | START PROJECT | All Rights Reserved |".

Figure 15: The News item about Issue 1 of the Newsletter.

Figure 16: The updated Multimedia page.

Figure 17: The updated Contact page.

5.5 START ON CONSORTIUM PARTNERS WEBSITES

Some partners have already included one or more pages about START in their respective websites.

5.5.1 LNEG website

On the website of LNEG, various pages have been created to document the existence and objectives of START in Portuguese and English. In the page about all LNEG projects (Figure 18²) START is now present, and by clicking there a specific page for the project is accessed (Figure 19³), that is also available in English (Figure 20⁴).

LNEG also published in the news the info about the approval of the project. This is available both in Portuguese (Figure 21⁵) and in English (Figure 22⁶).

² <https://www.lneg.pt/projetos/>

³ <https://www.lneg.pt/project/start-he/>

⁴ <https://www.lneg.pt/en/project/start-he-2/>

⁵ <https://www.lneg.pt/o-lneg-viu-recentemente-aprovados-projetos-no-horizon-europe/>

⁶ <https://www.lneg.pt/en/lneg-projects-recently-approved-in-horizon-europe/>

Figure 18: “Projects” page on LNEG website (in Portuguese).

LNEG INVESTIGAÇÃO PARA A SUSTENTABILIDADE

PT EN LOGN MENU

PROJETOS

- START

ÁREAS

- ENERGIA
- GEOLÓGIA E RECURSOS GEOLÓGICOS

CONHEÇA OS NOSSOS SERVIÇOS

SABER MAIS

START

pt WebSite: <https://www.lneg.pt/project/101058632>
 Data de Atualização: 22 setembro de 2022

SISTEMAS SUSTENTÁVEIS DE CAPTURA DE ENERGIA BASEADOS NUMA ABORDAGEM INOVADORA DE RECLICAGEM DE RESÍDUOS DE MINA.

O projeto START propõe uma solução tecnológica disruptiva assente na conversão de resíduos mineiros em materiais para recuperação de calor residual, contribuindo assim para uma utilização eficiente dos recursos ao mesmo tempo que incentiva a produção de energia verde por meio de dispositivos termoelétricos sustentáveis, em linha com as estratégias delineadas no Pacto Ecológico Europeu e nos Planos de Ação da UE para as Matérias-Primas Críticas e para a Economia Circular.

O objetivo principal do START é o de criar uma cadeia de valor sustentável e de um ecossistema de inovação associados ao desenvolvimento de dispositivos termoelétricos sem telúrio, com potenciais aplicações na indústria pesada e marítima ou como fonte de energia primária para sensores off-grid e dispositivos IoT. Tal será alcançado através da produção de semicondutores do tipo-p a partir do uso direto de minérios à base de tetraedrite, recolhidos em escombros de minas Europeias, de modo a substituir os semicondutores do tipo-p à base de telúrio. O projeto é coordenado pelo LNEG e agrega 15 organizações, de 10 estados membros da UE e de 1 país associado.

Período de execução: 01/06/2022 – 31/05/2026

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FICHEIROS RELACIONADOS

Ficha do projeto (https://www.lneg.pt/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/START_Ficheiro_PT.pdf)

UNIDADES DE INVESTIGAÇÃO

- UNIDADE DE MATERIAIS PARA A ENERGIA [VER MAIS](#)
- UNIDADE DE RECURSOS MINERAIS E GEOFÍSICA [VER MAIS](#)
- UNIDADE DE CIÊNCIA E TECNOLOGIA MINERAL [VER MAIS](#)
- UNIDADE DE ECONOMIA DE RECURSOS [VER MAIS](#)

LABORATÓRIOS

- Laboratório de Materiais e Revestimentos

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Figure 19: “START Project” page on LNEG website (in Portuguese).

LNEG RESEARCH FOR SUSTAINABILITY

PT EN LOGIN MENU

START

Homepage Projects **START**

PROJECTS

- START

AREAS

- ENERGY
- GEOLOGY AND GEOLOGICAL RESOURCES

START

Website: <https://www.start-iegproject.com>
 Last updated: 22 September, 2022

SUSTAINABLE ENERGY HARVESTING SYSTEMS BASED ON INNOVATIVE MINE WASTE RECYCLING

The START project proposes a unique technological solution, based on the conversion of mining waste into materials for waste heat recovery, thus contributing to an efficient use of resources while promoting the use of green energy harvesting through thermoelectrics, in line with the strategies outlined in the European Green Deal and in the EU Action Plans on Critical Raw Materials and on Circular Economy.

START project's primary objective is to build an innovation ecosystem in the EU related to the development of sustainable and economically viable tellurium-free thermoelectric waste heat harvesting systems, with potential applications in heavy industry, maritime industry or as primary power source for off-grid sensors and IoT devices. This will be achieved by producing advanced sulphide p-type TE thermoelements that incorporate discarded waste secondary sulphides (tetrahedrite), present in many European mine wastes, to replace the tellurium-based p-type TE thermoelements. The project is coordinated by LNEG and aggregates 15 organisations, from 10 EU member states and 1 associated country.

Project duration: 01/06/2022 – 31/05/2026
 Co-funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme.

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RELATED FILES

Project factsheet (https://www.lneg.pt/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/START_factsheet_EN-1.pdf)

RESEARCH UNITS

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Figure 20: “START Project” page on LNEG website (in English).

ÁREAS

- ENERGIA
- GEOLOGIA E RECURSOS GEOLÓGICOS

ÚLTIMAS NOTÍCIAS

- 1. GLOBAL SYMPOSIUM ON BIOENERGY AND BIREFINERIES**
04 novembro, 2022
- 2. "RECURSOS MINERAIS: MANTENDO O CONHECIMENTO, DESAFIOS E OPORTUNIDADES"**
31 outubro, 2022

Eventos

- 1. GREEN 2022 HYBRID BROKERAGE EVENT**
A realizar em: 23 novembro, 2022
até: 24 novembro, 2022
- 2. EVENTO DE DISSEMINAÇÃO DO PROJETO INTERREG SUDOE IMPROVEMENT**
A realizar em: 26 outubro, 2022
- 3. TRADERS 2ND PUBLIC WORKSHOP**
A realizar em: 28 novembro, 2022

RELACIONADOS

- MUST-READ
- NEWSLETTERS

O LNEG VIU RECENTEMENTE APROVADOS PROJETOS NO HORIZON EUROPE

17 de outubro de 2022

Categoria: Investigação, Notícias Internacionais

START – "Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling"

CO2struct – "Modelling the role of circular economy construction value chains for a carbon-neutral Europe"

CO2Hybrid – "Modelling the role of circular economy construction value chains for a carbon-neutral Europe"

A transição de sistemas de energia baseados no uso intensivo de combustíveis fósseis para sistemas de energia envolvendo a utilização intensiva de materiais implica uma maior necessidade de recursos minerais. Contudo, os minerais críticos que permitem esta transição energética estão geograficamente concentrados fora da Europa. Por outro lado, esta crescente procura por minerais essenciais e a diminuição da qualidade dos minérios tem conduzido a um aumento substancial nos volumes de resíduos das explorações minerais. Assim, a utilização de resíduos de minas, principalmente ao meio ambiente, como matérias primas secundárias para o desenvolvimento de dispositivos avançados de conversão de energia representa um forte incentivo económico e de proteção ambiental. Neste contexto, e em linha com as prioridades do Pacto Ecológico Europeu, o

Principais resultados esperados:

- Cadeia de valor inovadora o projeto START propõe tecnologias disruptivas para uso direto de minerais em ecossistemas de energia renovável termoelectrica, com base numa metodologia "waste material-waste heat to power".
- Nova oportunidade de mercado para os recursos minerais europeus: conversão recursos secundários descartados e amplamente disponíveis na Europa em matérias primas secundárias de elevado valor acrescentado.
- Reforçar a competitividade da UE em matéria de recursos: a reciclagem de resíduos de minas contribuirá para a segurança do aprovisionamento de matérias primas e para a sustentabilidade europeia.
- Ecossistemas de energia renovável: o projeto START permitirá a transição para uma sociedade e economia mais verdes por meio de ecossistemas, modelos económicos mais sustentáveis e promovendo a segurança energética.
- Novo ecossistema comercial: o projeto START criará um novo ecossistema comercial de rápido crescimento que atrairá novas partes interessadas explorando oportunidades de mercado para replicação e desenvolvimento de mercado.

Metodologia "waste material waste heat to power" projeto START.

CO2struct "Modelling the role of circular economy construction value chains for a carbon-neutral Europe" em que o LNEG integra um consórcio formado por várias instituições europeias e liderado pelo DTU (Technical University Denmark).

O projeto irá **integrar práticas de economia circular na modelação da mitigação de emissões de GEE** (usando o modelo TIMES para toda a Europa. Tem como caso de estudo seis materiais de construção tradicionais em carbono (cimento, aço, vidro, madeira, tijolo e materiais de isolamento) com enfoque em particular para a edifica off/hutec e edifícios, irá modelar o uso de recursos naturais para descarbonização numa lógica de economia circular.

Os **principais objetivos** do projeto prendem-se com a resposta às seguintes questões: Qual o impacto que medidas de Economia Circular podem ter na redução de emissões de GEE e nos custos associados? Quais os impactos para economia circular ao longo das cadeias de valor do cimento, aço, vidro, madeira, tijolo e materiais de isolamento que devem ser prioritários, para a aumentar a circularidade? Poderá a economia circular reduzir o impacto ambiental da mitigação climática dentro e fora do território da UE? Até que ponto a mitigação climática circular pode minorar danos para a saúde causados por emissões para ar e água de poluentes não-GEE? Quais as modificações necessárias em materiais/tecnologias/cadeias de valor que podem ser ativadas para alcançar a neutralidade carbónica?

Resultados esperados:

- desenvolvimento de uma framework de "mitigação climática circular" para tornar modelos de mitigação de GEE TIMES capazes de considerar a circularidade, como um ponto de partida para outros modelos de mitigação climática circulares;
- identificação de estratégias e medidas de economia circular para as principais indústrias (a cadeia de valor do cimento, aço, vidro, madeira, tijolo e materiais de isolamento);
- Soft-bank entre ferramentas de economia circular como análise ciclo de vida e material flow analysis e o modelo TIMES para a EIP;
- Desenho e análise de cenários de economia circular para quantificar o seu papel na mitigação climática da UE- no curto prazo e no futuro, sempre garantindo a neutralidade carbónica;
- contabilização de externalidades sociais e ambientais associadas à mitigação e implementação de estratégias de economia circular, incluindo emissões de GEE e poluentes atmosféricos, uso de água, energia incorporada, pobreza energética, emprego e desigualdades;
- informações úteis e eficazes de apoio a políticas públicas com vista à mitigação sustentável e custo-efiz.

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Figure 21: "Approval of START Project" page on LNEG website (in Portuguese).

AREAS

- ENERGY
- GEOLOGY AND GEOLOGICAL RESOURCES

LAST NEWS

- 1. REFUEC PORTUGAL 2022 BIOFUEL REGULATORS WORKSHOP**
21 October, 2022
- 2. EERA REPOWEREU MANIFESTO**
21 October, 2022

EVENTS

- 1. GREEN 2022 HYBRID BROKERAGE EVENT**
To be held on: 23 November, 2022
until: 24 November, 2022
- 2. TRADERES 2ND PUBLIC WORKSHOP**
To be held on: 28 November, 2022
- 3. LISBON BEYOND SUMMIT 2022**
To be held on: 3 November, 2022
until: 8 November, 2022

RELATED

- EVENTS
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LNEG PROJECTS RECENTLY APPROVED IN HORIZON EUROPE

Publication date: 17 January, 2022
Category: International News - Investigation

START – “Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling”

COconstruct – “Modelling the role of circular economy construction value chains for a carbon-neutral Europe”

START – “Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling” is coordinated by LNEG and composed by a consortium of 15 partners from 11 European countries (Portugal, Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Germany, Italy, Netherlands, Norway, Slovakia, Spain, Finland). The START project was approved within the scope of the Cluster 4: Digital Industry and Space; call HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01-07, will have a duration of 48 months and an eligible funding of €7.667.878,00, of which about 14% is allocated to LNEG.

The shift from a fuel-intensive to a material-intensive energy system implies an increased need of minerals. The critical minerals enabling this energy transition are geographically concentrated outside Europe when considering both extraction and processing operations. This growing demand for essential minerals and the declining quality of ores is leading to a substantial increase in waste volumes from mining operations. Employing mining residues as valuable secondary raw materials for advanced energy transition devices creates an increased economic incentive to eliminate environmentally hazardous tailings. Against this backdrop, and in line European Green Deal objectives, **START main objective** is to create a sustainable supply chain, and a corresponding business-innovation ecosystem, for tellurium-free thermoelectric harvesting devices based on

COconstruct “Modelling the role of circular economy construction value chains for a carbon-neutral Europe” where LNEG participates within a consortium of other six partners and led by DTU Technical University Denmark.

The project will integrate circular economy practices into the TIMES energy system G4G mitigation model for the whole of Europe. It is focused on six carbon-intensive and pervasive construction materials (cement, steel, wood, brick and insulation materials), with a particular focus on 2 clusters: offshore wind and buildings. It will model the use of natural resources for decarbonization using a circular economy approach.

The main **objectives** of the project include answering the following questions: How much can CE measures impact GHG abatement and energy costs? Which are the value chain hotspots for CE that should be prioritized? Can CE lower the environmental impact of climate mitigation (inside and outside EU)? Can circular climate mitigation abate health damage of non-GHG emissions to air and water? What are the necessary modifications in materials/techniques/value-chains that can be leveraged to achieve carbon neutrality?

Main results expected:

- Delineation of a “circular climate mitigation” framework to augment TIMES models at a first stage, but that can serve as an input for other climate mitigation models.
- Identification of circular economy measures in the key industries of the six materials’ value chains.
- Mapping six value chains with explicit feedback loops and quantified rebound effects, key of circular economy practices.
- Assessment of social and environmental externalities of mitigation and of circular economy practices, including GHG & air pollutants emissions, water usage, embodied energy, energy poverty, employment, and inequalities.
- Coupling of circular economy tools, as life-cycle analysis and material flow analysis, with the TIMES model.
- Quantification of the role of CE for EU climate mitigation in the near-term and future, always ensuring carbon neutrality.
- Useful and effective policy support information for sustainable climate mitigation, minimizing conflicts across SDGs (both in EU- and rest of the world).

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Figure 22: “Approval of START Project” page on LNEG website (in English).

5.5.2 ASGMI website

On the ASGMI website, START has been mentioned in the occasion of the Kick-off meeting (KoM), both in Spanish (Figure 23⁷) and in English (Figure 24).

Figure 23: “Kick-off of START Project” page on ASGMI website (in Spanish).

⁷ <https://asgmi.org/inicio-del-proyecto-start/> (also valid for the English version)

ASGMI
Asociación de Servicios de Geología y Minería Iberoamericana

ORGANISATION MEMBERS GENERAL ASSEMBLY WORKSHOPS CONTACT LANGUAGE

START PROJECT

28 JUNE, 2022 PCR ASGMI

Social media icons: YouTube, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram

We are very proud to announce the official beginning of the START project, which took place on June 1st, 2022, with the kick off meeting held on June 21 and 22 in LNEG, Lisbon, Portugal. START, which stands for "Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling", with the concept of transforming mining waste into materials for waste heat recovery, will create a sustainable supply chain and a corresponding business-innovation ecosystem for tellurium-free thermoelectric green energy harvesting products based on secondary raw materials responsibly sourced from within the European Union (EU).

START is an innovation action project supported by the EU and its Horizon Europe programme (HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01-07). The Consortium comprises 15 multidisciplinary institutions with large experience in international innovation projects: LNEG (coordinator), 3drivers, ASGMI, BGR, EPMA, GenCore, GEO-U, GBA, LPRC, MBN, RGS, SQUJOS, SINTEF, Technology and IGME-CSIC. The START project have a total duration of 48 months and 9 194 441.25 € of total eligible costs.

FILED UNDER: NOTICIAS, PROYECTOS

THE GEERA RAW MATERIALS MONODGRAPH

(ESPAÑOL) WEBINAR "EL PAPEL DEL COBRE EN LA ENERGÍA LIMPIA Y TRANSICIÓN DIGITAL"

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START

ASGMI PROJECTS
MAMAC, PAM

(Español) MAPA METALOGÉNICO DE AMÉRICA CENTRAL Y EL CARIBE.

LAST NEWS
(Español) Celebración del Primer Día Internacional de la Geodiversidad Thursday October 6th, 2022
(Español) Taller "Información Geoquímica para la Sociedad" – 19-23 septiembre, Medellín Thursday September 8th, 2022

ALL NEWS

DOCUMENTS

DOCUMENTS ELABORATED BY THE EXPERTS GROUP ON GEOLOGICAL HERITAGE:
Bases para el desarrollo común del Patrimonio Geológico en los Servicios Geológicos de Iberoamérica

DOCUMENTS ELABORATED BY THE EXPERT GROUP ON MINING ENVIRONMENTAL LIABILITIES:
Pasivos Ambientales Mineros. Manual para el Inventario de Minas Abandonadas o Paralizadas.
Conocimiento y percepciones acerca de los pasivos ambientales mineros (PAM) en países miembros de la Asociación de Servicios de Geología y Minería Iberoamericanos (ASGMI)
Glosario Técnico en Materia de Gestión de Pasivos Ambientales Mineros

Asociación de Servicios de Geología y Minería - ASGMI

Figure 24: "Kick-off of START Project" page on ASGMI website (in English).

5.5.3 LPRC website

LPRC published info about START, too. In the "projects" page (Figure 25⁸) START is listed, and by clicking on the link, one is taken to a page describing the project (Figure 26⁹). There is also a piece of news describing the KoM (Figure 27¹⁰).

⁸ <https://www.lapalmacentre.eu/projects/>

⁹ <https://www.lapalmacentre.eu/portfolio-item/start/>

¹⁰ <https://www.lapalmacentre.eu/start-kick-off-meeting-lisbon-20-21-june-2022/>

Figure 25: "Projects" page on LPRC website.

The screenshot shows the LPRC website page for the START project. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the LPRC logo and links for 'About us', 'Projects', 'News', 'Contact Us', 'En Español', and 'En Français'. Below this, a breadcrumb trail indicates the current location: 'Home / LPRC Projects / START'. The main content area features a large 'START' logo and a photograph of a person presenting in a conference room. To the right of the photo, there is a 'Fact sheet' section with the following details:

- Name:** START – Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling
- Program:** HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01
- Budget:** EUR 9 194.441
- Duration:** 01/06/2022- 31/05/2026

Below the fact sheet is an 'About the project' section, followed by 'Our role in the project' and 'More information'. The 'More information' section provides contact details for Luis Lopes at luislopes_at_lapalmacentre.eu. At the bottom of the main content area, there is a section titled 'Other projects' which displays a grid of logos for various other projects: CRM-Geothermal, START, EMPORIA4KT, RAVEN, TIMREX, MACARONIGHT, INCORE, FUTUR, UNEXUP, and MOBI-US. The MOBI-US project is described as 'A structured mobility network among raw materials-related Master programs in the East & South-East European countries'. The footer of the page includes a copyright notice and social media links.

Figure 26: Page on the START project on the LPRC website.

The screenshot shows the LPRC website page for the START kick-off meeting. The header includes the LPRC logo and navigation links: About us, Projects, News, Contact Us, En Español, En Français. The main content area features a photo of the meeting and the following text:

START Kick-off meeting, Lisbon, 20-21 June 2022
 27th June 2022 / in News / by Luis Lopes

We are very proud to announce the official beginning of the START project, which took place on June 1st, 2022, with the Kick-off meeting held on June 20 and 21 in LNEG, Lisbon, Portugal. START, which stands for "Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling", with the concept of transforming mining waste into materials for waste heat recovery, will create a sustainable supply chain and a corresponding business-innovation ecosystem for tellurium-free thermoelectric green energy harvesting products based on secondary raw materials responsibly sourced from within the European Union (EU).

START is an Innovation Action project supported by the EU and its Horizon Europe programme (HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01-07). The Consortium comprises 15 multidisciplinary institutions with large experience in international innovation projects: LNEG (coordinator), 3drivers, ASGMI, BGR, EPMA, GeniCore, GEO-U, GBA, LPRC, MBN, RGS, SGUDS, SINTEF, TEGnology and IGME-CSIC. The START project have a total duration of 48 months and 9 194 441.25 € of total eligible costs.

The project partners – including LPRC represented by Luis Lopes – discussed the implementation of the seven Work Packages throughout the meeting days. The Work packages are:

1. Coordination and management
2. Selection of mine waste sites; physical minerals separation and concentration
3. Materials modelling and processing
4. Materials characterization
5. Device production, validation and demonstration
6. Dissemination and communication
7. Innovation and exploitation strategy

LPRC is the leader of Work Package 7 and all its four tasks. In this part of the project, LPRC will implement a foresight exercise for the development of a flexible, scalable and adaptable business case design for the START value chain, document industrial viability and economics, develop a business focused roadmap and develop sustainability plans. LPRC also participates in Work Packages 2, 5 and 6.

START started in June 2022 and will end in May 2026 (48-month project duration). There is a long way to go, full of work ahead.

Keep informed by following the project website and social media channels.

Tags: Recycling, START

The right sidebar contains a TAGS section with various project-related tags and a calendar for November 2022.

November 2022						
M	T	W	T	F	S	S
	1	2	3	4	5	6
7	8	9	10	11	12	13
14	15	16	17	18	19	20
21	22	23	24	25	26	27
28	29	30				

Figure 27: Page on the START kick-off meeting on the LPRC website.

5.5.4 EPMA website and newsletters

In the EPMA website, a page dedicated to the project has been created. It contains a short description of its concept and of the consortium. The text includes the link to the project website and the invitation to subscribe its mailing list.

The address of the mentioned page is the following: <https://www.epma.com/projects/start-project>.

In the weekly newsletter, EPMA is also sending regularly to about 1600 member contacts the project website link, and in the issue sent out on 29 November also a link to download the START newsletter from the website. In the quarterly newsletter #126, issued on 16th November 2022 with the same distribution, a summary about the project, with an invitation to check the website and subscribe there, has been included (Figure 29). In the next editions of this quarterly document, EPMA will continue to inform its members about the progress in START's activities, including the link to download the START Newsletter.

Figure 28: Page dedicated to START on EPMA's website.

European Projects

European Project (Continued)

START, a new Horizon Europe project in EPMA's portfolio

As already mentioned, the Horizon Europe new research programme brought within EPMA activities a new major project, START ("Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling"). The project began on 1st June 2022 (duration 48 months), and a kick-off meeting was held in Lisbon on 20-21 June.

The START topic falls within the area of Functional materials, and namely of thermoelectric materials. These materials transform a temperature difference into an electrical current, and can be used to convert unused, wasted heat, for instance from industrial processes, or from appliances (or even large hot surfaces like a city road in the summer), to improve process efficiency, or to power off-grid sensors and devices. The additional plus of the project, that already aims at improving energy efficiency, is to use minerals that currently are stockpiled as wastes from mining operations (e.g., in copper mines), because they were just scrapped as contaminants for the main production. These minerals, tetrahedrites that belong to the largest family of sulphides, with the general chemical formula $Cu_2[Cu^{TM}]_2Sb_2S_{11}$ where TM is a transition metal, have already been tested in previous lab scale experiences and proved to be a good candidate to replace the usual commercial thermoelectric materials, that normally contain tellurium, an element that comes almost only from the Far East and that will be under further significant pressure in the next decades because of the increasing use for the green technologies.

Thus, the project offers a further step in the direction of Europe's reduced dependence from Critical Raw Materials, by increasing resource productivity and decreasing waste in line with the new Circular Economy Action Plan.

The project is coordinated by LNEG (Portugal); it includes 15 organisations (6 RTDs, 7 SMEs, 2 non-profit international associations – one being EPMA) from 10 EU member states and 1 associated country, with strong background and knowledge on geology, materials science and renewable energies.

As usual in EU funded projects, EPMA is responsible for the Dissemination and Communication activities. For instance, a booth was present at World

PM2022 in Lyon. The coordinator F. Neves of LNEG gave two presentations during the congress & exhibition, one in the Industry Corner and one at the Sectoral Group Meeting of the EuroFM (Functional Materials).

If you are interested in the project, check out its website www.START-HEproject.com, and find out more; you can follow also on Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, etc. Subscribing to the mailing list on the website will allow to receive directly news about the project, and in particular the newsletter, whose first issue is due in November 2022 and that will be published twice per year.

EPMA Training News

Summer School 2023

The European Powder Metallurgy Association will hold its 21st Powder Metallurgy Summer School in Dresden, Germany, from 17 to 21 July 2023 in Fraunhofer Institute for Manufacturing Technology and Advanced Materials (IFAM). The five-day programme will be hosted and coordinated by Dr. Christian Gierl-Mayer, TU Wien, Austria, and Dr. Marco Actis-Grande, Politecnico di Torino, Italy.

The programme will be delivered by a range of specialists from both industry and academia, whose expertise reflect many key topics currently being employed in today's Powder Metallurgy industry. The course includes group problem solving sessions and laboratory work and a site visit. More information about the programme will be available in December on the event website.

The summer school will also include some social events such as the welcome reception on Monday evening and its networking dinner.

Application for the Summer School 2023 will open on 17 January 2023, please visit our website for more information

Application deadline : 3 May 2023

Young Engineers 2023

WorldPM2023 hosted the Young Engineers Days programme on 10 & 11 October 2022 in Lyon, France. Introduced in 2014, this programme is run every year as a part of EPMA's commitment to help foster and develop the next generation of PM academics and industrialists. This year's edition was attended by 23 young engineers coming from France, UK, Germany, Belgium, Sweden, Spain, Turkey and South Africa. The students benefited from lectures on the PM process and Q&A sessions with industry experts; they also had the opportunity to visit many stands of the Exhibition in order to have a better understanding of the PM industry and they ended their two days with the visit of the INSA (Institut National des Sciences Appliquées) nearby the Congress center. On the 10th October evening, they had the opportunity to relax and have fun in a Cuban-style restaurant where most of them also enjoyed some salsa dancing. The feedback given by the group was very positive: students were happy with the two intensive days where they said they learnt a lot while having some fun and enjoying the opportunity to network and make new connections with people their age and sharing the same interest.

Next year's edition will take place on October 2 & 3, 2023 during EuroPM2023 in Lisbon, Portugal.

Figure 29: EPMA Newsletter #126, November 2022, page 8.

5.6 SOCIAL MEDIA

The project's social media accounts have been already created and reported in deliverable D6.1 ("Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools"), submitted on 29th July 2022. The social media activated are:

- Twitter (partner responsible: LPRC): https://twitter.com/START_HEproject
- LinkedIn (EPMA): <https://www.linkedin.com/company/86266991/>
- YouTube (EPMA): <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCHVjEhpVz9uaEgzICj2InPA>
- Twitch (LPRC): https://www.twitch.tv/start_he_project

- SlideShare (ASGMI): <https://es.slideshare.net/StartProject/>

In addition to these, an account on the Zenodo service¹¹, the Open Data service created by CERN within the OpenAIRE project in 2013, that also offers the creation of a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) number, has been created (see for instance the document [Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling | Zenodo](#)) by LNEG and will be used, in parallel with SlideShare, to get open access to the START documents (see chapter 6.4).

Social media are used to engage the audience, bring them to the website, and in general to disseminate and communicate (also to the wider public) about START activities, results and partners.

5.6.1 Activity on Twitter

During M01-M06 a total of 14 posts (and 3 retweets) were made, spanning from 07/07/2022 to 23/11/2022, and contributing to the following statistics:

- 1) Number of Followers: 37
- 2) Total number of views/Impressions: 5,522
- 3) Total number of Audience (counted as Engagements + Detail Expands + New followers + Profile visits + Link clicks + Likes + Retweets): 492

The START Twitter posts aimed at sharing information with the community on the project's goals, objectives, and concept, as well as on the relevant communication activities such as presentations at conferences, the START video and online materials. Despite the relatively low number of followers, the Twitter posts were seen 5522 times (an average of ~400 views per post), which are relatively good numbers for a project that just started. Figure 30 shows the "homepage" of the START Twitter account.

¹¹ <https://zenodo.org/>

Figure 30: The START Twitter profile (status on 23/11/2022).

5.6.2 Activity on LinkedIn

The activity on LinkedIn went along two main lines:

- Achieving a larger audience for the START page. This was done mainly by EPMA, using the network available to them. At the date of writing this report (29 November 2022), the page followers are 142 (Figure 31).
- Posting project news to bring interest and send interested people to the website, if possible, to let them subscribe to the project's mailing list.

Figure 31: LinkedIn START followers since project start and until mid-November 2022 (no “sponsored” followers are present, only “organic”, i.e., normal).

Concerning posts, in the period between 27/06/2022 and 15/11/2022 there were:

- 9 posts on the START page
- 5 pages on LinkedIn groups (the large “EPMA networking group”, the “Sustainability professionals” group, and the “Thermoelectrics” group)

plus, more posts on personal accounts (surely more than 10 and probably in the range of 20) by members of the consortium, that have been only partly considered in the evaluation of impact.

The plan here is similar to Twitter’s, with the difference that LinkedIn is a business-oriented platform, so most readers are professionals, coming firstly from the contacts of the LinkedIn administrating entities and then, in further waves, from their contacts. So, we expect the audience to grow slowly at the start, and then improve over time when the contents will be spread over a growing basis of followers and be visible to their contacts.

5.6.3 Activity on YouTube

The only activity on YouTube to date was the publication of the Introductory video (see chapter) on 25th October 2022. In the first 22 days from publication (25/10/2022-15/11/2022), the video had 75 visualisations from 48 unique visitors, only one of which subscribed to the channel. A peak of views was after 7 November, in connection with some important dissemination events and social media coverage. The analysis of visualisation behaviour shows that 34.4% of the users actually visualised the video until the end, whereas the average duration of the views is 30 seconds. That would indicate that shorter video can be more effective, but the content of the video could not be conveyed in a significantly shorter time, in this case.

5.6.4 Activity on Twitch

Twitch has not been used yet.

5.6.5 Activity on SlideShare

SlideShare has been used to host six documents prepared that were also uploaded to the website, and some on Zenodo (see also chapter 5.4 and chapter 6.4):

- “Green energy harvesting – State of the art”
- “Project START: From WASTE to HIGH-TECH”, presentation at EU-Latin America Raw Materials Convention 2022 (Santiago de Chile, 3-4 November 2022) given by Daniel de Oliveira (LNEG).
- Presentation at World PM 2022 (Lyon, 9-13 October 2022) given by Filipe Neves (LNEG).
- START Factsheet in Portuguese.
- START Factsheet in English.
- START Flyer.

5.7 MATERIALS FOR BOOTHS/PHYSICAL DISTRIBUTION

It was envisaged that some material had to be produced during the project in order to be shown and in some cases distributed to interested people in physical events. This includes informative material (like leaflets that are consumables, but also reusable like posters and banners) and also small gadgets that will carry at least the project logo and thus might attract people to search for more information later.

The informative material is also intended to be used in its digital version for the website and for other uses.

5.7.1 Leaflet(s)

Leaflets for the project have already been produced, and will be produced in later versions, both in pdf and in print. In all versions, they will generally be in A5 size, two-sided. The final leaflet, containing more technical information about the results achieved, may need more room; so possibly a 4-page A5 sized leaflet will be prepared. All this material will be available for download from the website and distributed at physical events. As a general «lean» approach, though, printed copies will be limited in number and digital download will be encouraged to reduce paper waste. QR codes will be offered to scan, with direct link to the downloadable materials. If a partner needs to print a specific leaflet, the printable files will be available (InDesign format).

These will be the different versions foreseen for the leaflets:

- Version 1 at early stages (already produced)
- Version 2 at midterm (M24, May 2024)
- Version 3, final, at project end M46 (March 2026) for distribution during the final event and other concluding events

According to this plan, a version 1, or “initial” leaflet has been prepared, using mainly the information that was already available. Due to the preliminary stage of the project, the only info that can be conveyed in this leaflet is the awareness of the project and of its scope and importance, the consortium partners and the coordinates of the website to reach for more details.

The two sides of the Initial START leaflet, whose final version was available, after check from the ExCom, at the end of M03, are shown in Figure 32 and Figure 33 (ready-to-print version, with the crop marks for correct cutting).

250 copies of the leaflet were printed by EPMA, but the partners can access the ready-to print file on the project's SharePoint and print them on their own for any dissemination purposes.

Unfortunately, it was not possible to print copies of the leaflet before mid-September, so the first event in which they have been used for dissemination is the World PM 2022 in Lyon (see chapter 6.2.5), and then the EU-Latin America Raw Materials Convention in Chile (see chapter 6.2.6).

Versions 2 and 3 will be prepared later in the project as explained, and in case further versions can be organised if any special need arises.

START: SUSTAINABLE ENERGY HARVESTING SYSTEMS BASED ON INNOVATIVE MINE WASTE RECYCLING

PRIMARY OBJECTIVE

To build an innovation ecosystem in the European Union (EU) related to the development of sustainable and economically viable tellurium-free thermoelectric (TE) waste heat harvesting systems, to be applied in heavy industry, maritime industry and also as primary power source for off-grid sensors and IoT devices.

HOW WILL IT BE ACHIEVED?

By incorporating sulphides (mainly tetrahedrite mineral series), at present an environment hazard in mine tailings, collected in five European countries, in the production of advanced sulphide p-type TE thermoelements. In contrast, current commercial TE devices incorporate p-type and n-type TE thermoelements that are produced from expensive and rare elements, namely tellurium, which is predominantly sourced in China.

EXPECTED IMPACT

The impact of START project's approach on endorsing a more sustainable and resilient EU comes from three inputs.

First, by reducing EU's dependence on primary critical raw materials.

Secondly, through the promotion of circular economy processes that will create value in EU by building a strategic ecosystem based on a high-abundant mineral.

Thirdly, by the production of TE energy harvesting systems offering a contribution to the reduction of fossil fuels consumption with a great impact on the increase of the overall efficiency of energy production and consumption systems, as well as on the reduction of the greenhouse gas emissions.

DURATION 01 June 2022 – 31 May 2026

BUDGET 9.2 M€

START CONCEPT

Figure 32: START Initial A5 leaflet, recto.

START: SUSTAINABLE ENERGY HARVESTING SYSTEMS BASED ON INNOVATIVE MINE WASTE RECYCLING

THE START CONSORTIUM

The project is coordinated by LNEG (Portugal) and aggregates 15 organisations, from 10 EU member states and 1 associated country, including: 6 research organizations with strong background and knowledge on geology, materials science and renewable energies; 7 SME's companies that guarantee the entire supply chain, from production, exploitation and ecological footprint assessment; and 2 non-profit international associations with a consolidated network of partners and stakeholders.

www.START-HEproject.com

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Figure 33: START Initial A5 leaflet, verso.

5.7.2 Roller banner(s)

Roller banners, or rollups, are self-standing “vertical” elements (typically 2 m high, 0.85 m wide) that usually show rather generic info about the project, for instance the logo of the project and of the partners, diagrams with explanation of the project’s workflow and basic principles, images

showing devices or parts, etc., accompanied by simple text that can be read in a short time (e.g., while walking in front of a booth). They are normally used in booths or in the rooms when a project event is happening, so that the project logo is continuously visible for the participants.

It was planned to print initially a generic roller banner with the basic information about the project, that will be used along the project every time that a project booth will be set up in an event.

The work on the banner was carried out by EPMA during M03, August 2022, and after the needed check with the ExCom, the final version was ready for printing in September.

The “Initial roller banner” is visible in Figure 34.

START

START – Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling

Primary objective: Build an European innovation ecosystem for thermoelectric (TE) waste heat harvesting systems

SCHEMATICS OF A THERMOELECTRICAL MODULE

How: By incorporating **sulphides (tetrahedrite)**, present in many **European mine wastes**, into advanced sulphide p-type TE thermoelements.

Expected impact towards a more **sustainable and resilient EU**:

- **Reducing EU dependence** on primary critical raw materials
- **Promotion of circular economy** processes
- **Production** of TE energy harvesting systems to:
 - ✓ **reduce fossil fuels consumption**
 - ✓ **increase overall efficiency** of energy production and consumption systems
 - ✓ **reduce greenhouse gas emissions**

START CONCEPT

Duration: 01 June 2022 – 31 May 2026 | Budget: 9.2 M€

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Figure 34: START Initial roller banner.

Two copies of the Initial roller banner were printed and used by EPMA in the START booth at World PM2022 in Lyon (see chapter 6.2.5).

At least one more roller banner will be prepared, after midterm, with some highlights of results obtained until then.

The banners are reusable, but wear and tear (for instance during shipping) could lead to the need to reprint them. In that case, a review of the content could be done.

5.7.3 *Poster(s) and other banners*

Like for the leaflets and roller banners, EPMA took the job of preparing a set of posters and other banners.

As a principle, posters can be of different approach: if used in a set, each poster can have a specific content. A poster could just show the project logo, or consortium partners. Others could be more verbose, and explain more about the project approach, specific results, etc. It was imagined that at least 3-4 different posters might be needed for exhibiting in booth or as poster presentations in some event.

EPMA prepared many graphic files that have already been used in different occasions.

EPMA undertakes the printing of the posters needed for the events where EPMA takes part; but all partners will be able to access the printable files and use them in events where they go on their own, by printing them (the cost for shipping is quite likely higher than a reprint). Also, wear and tear are very probable, so new copies will likely be printed during the project. Clearly, when specific posters have been prepared for specific events, the partners participating have taken care, in case, of the printing.

5.7.3.1 *“Initial” posters set*

EPMA prepared the files for a set of for 4 A0 portrait posters, that are an “Initial” set, with just the project’s description.

The first of these is just a “title and logo” poster (Figure 35), with very little information on the project apart from the project co-funding programme and the project website.

The second poster (Figure 36) describes project’s objectives, expected impact and shows again the website.

The third poster (Figure 37) includes the flow diagram that explains the concept behind the project (and quotes the website).

The fourth poster (Figure 38) shows a map of Europe with the different partners and shows again the website.

Used all together, the posters give full information, yet without long sentences and explanations, about the project.

The set has been printed by EPMA on plastic material, to have them more durable, and has been already used in the START booth at the World PM2022 in Lyon (see chapter 6.2.5).

Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling

A HORIZON EUROPE PROJECT
PROJECT: 101058632 (HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01)

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Figure 35: START poster 01: title, info and website.

Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling

A HORIZON EUROPE PROJECT
PROJECT: 101058632 (HORIZON CL4 2021 RESILIENCE 01)

What are our objectives?

PRIMARY OBJECTIVE

Build an European innovation ecosystem based on the development of sustainable and economically viable thermoelectric (TE) waste heat harvesting systems applied in heavy and maritime industry, and as primary power source for off-grid sensors and IoT devices.

TO BE ACHIEVED by incorporating sulphides (tetrahedrite), present in many European mine wastes, into advanced sulphide p-type TE thermoelements, thereby reducing tellurium dependence from non-European countries.

EXPECTED IMPACT towards a more sustainable and resilient EU:

- **Reducing EU dependence** on primary critical raw materials (tellurium).
- Promotion of **circular economy processes** building a strategic ecosystem based on a high-abundant mineral (single phase p-type tetrahedrite).
- Production of TE **energy harvesting** systems to:
 - ✓ reduce fossil fuels consumption
 - ✓ increase overall efficiency of energy production and consumption systems
 - ✓ reduce greenhouse gas emissions

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Figure 36: START poster 02: objectives, expected impact and website.

Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling

A HORIZON EUROPE PROJECT
PROJECT: 101058632 (HORIZON CL4 2021 RESILIENCE 01)

What is the START Project?

START CONCEPT

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Figure 37: START poster 03: concept flowchart and website.

**Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on
innovative mine waste recycling**

A HORIZON EUROPE PROJECT
PROJECT: 101058632 (HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01)

Who are the START Partners?

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Figure 38: START poster 04: consortium and website.

5.7.3.2 *Other posters and banners*

For some specific events, other materials, posters and banners, have been prepared by EPMA, mostly as digital documents and not for printing.

For the 1st Conference of IGME-CSIC (see chapter 6.2.1), a landscape poster was prepared, that was used to present the project during the meeting.

For the event Perumin (see chapter 6.2.3), a banner in Spanish was prepared, visible in Figure 40. According to the requirements of the organizers, this banner was shown in the EC stand. No information is there, apart from the QR code that sends to the START website.

For the event EU-Latin America RM (see chapter 6.2.6) a tall banner was prepared (Figure 41), with just an additional image of minerals, no specific details apart from the QR code linking to the project website.

For the event Raw Materials Week 2022 (see chapter 6.2.8) a portrait poster was prepared (Figure 42), starting from the “initial roller banner” contents.

Figure 39: Poster about START created for the 1st Conference of IGME-CSIC, July 2022.

Figure 40: Banner for the Perumin 2022 event.

Sistemas sostenibles de extracción de energía basados en el reciclaje innovador de escombreras mineras

© Fabre Minerals

Escanea el QR code y conoce mas :

Visita:
www.start-heproject.com
start@lneg.pt

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Figure 41: START banner for the event EU-Latin America RM 2022.

START – Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling

Primary objective: Build an European innovation ecosystem for thermoelectric (TE) waste heat harvesting systems.

How: By incorporating **sulphides (tetrahedrite)**, present in many **European mine wastes**, into advanced sulphide p-type TE materials.

Expected impact towards a more **sustainable and resilient EU**:

- **Reducing EU dependence** on primary critical raw materials
- **Promotion of circular economy** processes
- **Efficiency of energy production and consumption systems**, with reduction of fossil fuels consumption and greenhouse gas emissions

SCHEMATICS OF A THERMOELECTRICAL MODULE

START CONCEPT

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Figure 42: START poster for the event Raw Materials Week 2022.

5.7.4 Consumables

Gadgets will be considered, to be distributed at exhibitions and START events. Examples: pens, bags, USB sticks with project info, etc. The gadgets will have project’s logo and website and if possible, should be in line with the project’s approach, recalling sustainability aspects.

For the moment, no consumable has been produced.

5.8 START NEWSLETTER

The project has a Newsletter that is published on its website and social media every 6 months, starting from Issue 1 at M06. To give more appeal to the newsletter, the consortium chose a name that is suggesting that the content will not be just related to START but will be strictly connected with the sustainability solutions imagined. The name was decided among the consortium before the first issue was prepared: “RECOVER – REFORM - REUSE”. This brings in the ideas of recovering (mine wastes, heat), of transformation (of wastes into raw materials for thermoelectric devices, of otherwise dispersed heat into electrical energy), and of reusing (materials and energy achieved to obtain better efficiency).

The information conveyed in the various issues of the newsletter will in fact include:

- General information about START, thermoelectric materials, energy harvesting from waste heat, and linked sustainability topics, including state-of-the-art documents and scientific reviews
- Updates on project activities
- Updates on project events and other dissemination topics, with invitation to join events where START will be featured
- Description of consortium partners (typically 2 per issue)
- All information on the various ways to keep informed about START (links to website, social media, link to the contact and subscription forms, etc.)

It is likely that with the progress in the project, and the need to stimulate exploitation, the length of the publication will increase.

Being completely public, the information in the Newsletter must be duly checked in order to avoid IPR management issues.

The distribution is partly based on a list of subscribers. To create this list, the website tool for registration is used, and social media posts attract new subscribers to the website tool.

5.8.1 Newsletter issue #1

The Issue 1 of the newsletter was prepared in the months of October/November 2022. EPMA created a template for the publication that will be used in all subsequent issues. It is a simple template, very similar to the template already used for documents.

The content of the issue is as follows:

1. Editorial from the coordinator
2. Starty explains START
3. START chronicles: START begins and plans big things
 - 3.1. LNEG hosted the kick-off meeting
 - 3.2. Work package 2: initial work In Austria, Portugal and Spain
 - 3.3. START joins several events in Europe and South America
4. Technical Pills
 - 4.1. Critical minerals and raw materials sustainability in the EU
 - 4.2. What is a thermoelectric material?
5. Consortium Tour

- 5.1. LNEG
- 5.2. SINTEF
- 6. Contacts

The total size of this issue #1 is 11 pages. A full version is available in Annex I.

The newsletter was uploaded to the website (28 November 2022) on the Documents page (with reference also in the News page) and was uploaded also to Zenodo¹² (29 November 2022). It was advertised on Twitter (29 November 2022) and LinkedIn (29 November 2022). A news item on the EPMA quarterly newsletter has been sent to all EPMA members (about 1600 contacts). The launch of Issue 1 was announced on the EPMA weekly Newsletter for members on 29 November 2022 (Figure 43, Figure 44) and will be announced later to non-members (about 1600 and 400 contacts, respectively). The data for downloads will be analysed in the next weeks.

[View in browser](#)

Weekly News

EURO PM2023
CONGRESS & EXHIBITION
1-4 October 2023, Lisbon Congress Centre

@Euro_PM #europm2023
www.europm2023.com

EPMA News

START Project Newsletter #1 Now Available

The Horizon Europe project START on recovery of wasted heat with thermoelectric devices built from recovered mine wastes, in which EPMA is involved, has published the first issue of its newsletter.

[Read More >](#)

Euro PM2023 Call for Papers

Submit your abstract ahead of the 18 January 2023 deadline and take part in next year's PM Congress.

[Read More >](#)

Industry News

Figure 43: EPMA weekly Newsletter 29 November 2022, with the news about the Newsletter Issue 1, the link leads to Figure 44.

¹² 10.5281/zenodo.7377126

Figure 44: EPMA news item of 29 November 2022, with the news about the Newsletter Issue 1 (linked in the EPMA newsletter of Figure 43).

5.9 START COMICS - STARTY

As already explained in previous Deliverables, START is making use of a comics character that will be employed as much as possible to make communication more appealing also to those categories in the target that are not too scientifically involved in the subject, including the general public. This character will guide the reader into the START contents and its development has been planned for roughly the first year of the project (Table 2).

Table 2: Plan to develop START comics.

ACTION	Q1 (Sep22-Nov22)	Q2 (Dec22-Feb23)	Q3 (Mar23-May23)	Q4 (Jun23-Aug23)
Content Development				
Character Development				
Story board				
Drawing pages				
Animation				
Tests & Release				

The final name is “Starty, the robot” (Figure 45). It is a robot that moves on a single wheel, has arms, an antenna, a large “screen” on its face where the project logo appears, and sometimes the robot’s emotions, and an emblem of a yellow star with blue outline (recalling the EU logo) on its chest. Starty loves the environment and the planet, is at ease with mines and excavators, and likes to spare energy and resources!

Figure 45: Some images of Starty, our robotic testimonial comics character.

Starty already “starred” in the introductory video developed in September 2022, where it explained the concept of the project and that has been and will be used in events, where possible. A first storyboard with Starty as main character was featured on the first issue of the START Newsletter “RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE” issued in November 2022 (Figure 46).

Figure 46: The first Starty strip, included in the START Newsletter #1, November 2022.

5.10 VIDEOS

According to what was planned in the proposal, at least 5 videos will be produced during the project:

- 2 short videos (0.5-1 min), one at the start of the project to raise awareness and one at the end to summarise results. The language should be suitable for a wider audience; animations or cartoons could be used to attract non-specialists. One video at M04 (September 2022), one at M48 (May 2026).
- 2 longer videos (but still not too long, max 3 min) during the project, focusing on project topics and activities. The target should be more to groups 2-3, i.e., scientists, engineers, and entrepreneurs. Both videos are due at M48 (May 2026)
- 1 detailed video (about 5 min) at mid project (M24, May 2024), highlighting the results of the first part of the project.

Other videos could be produced, like:

- Interviews with key partners, describing the project or specific topics
- Recording of presentations given in events
- Short ads for specific events or for the “serious game”

EPMA will be taking care of producing the videos but will ask all relevant partners to help by delivering videos, images, and text.

The videos will be hosted on YouTube and Twitch, will be embedded in the START website, and posted on other social media like LinkedIn and Twitter.

The KPIs decided for these tools are basically views. A minimum of 100 views per video is the base KPI, and an overall average above 200 views/video is an additional KPI. Clearly, the different social media analysis tools allow collecting even further information about the audience.

5.10.1 Video 1 - START introductory video (M04)

As originally planned, a short introductory video for the project has been created in September 2022.

The structure of the video is similar to a slideshow with animations: the aim is to give the few important information about the project, i.e., its basic approach, the planned activity, the consortium and the expected impact. To do that without being too serious it was decided to use Starty, our robot testimonial, to give the info in the form of balloons in every slide, together with some pictures and animations that better explain the concepts.

EPMA prepared first a conceptual draft (an animated slideshow on PowerPoint); then, following the opinion of the partners, a final version of the video was produced (with the software AfterEffects). Finally, the video was also audio dubbed by adding a commercial music track (“Advertising” by Masluk Vladislav), whose rights have been bought.

The video was then uploaded to the START YouTube page (<https://youtu.be/-x8XGUrVAfs>), embedded in the START website, on the home page and in the Multimedia page, and posted to LinkedIn and Twitter.

In the following figures, the main moments of the video are visible:

1. The first scene with title and main info (Figure 47)
2. Starty introduces itself (Figure 48)
3. Starty explains the basic idea behind START, using thermoelectric generators to recover waste heat by using minerals from mine wastes (Figure 49)
4. Starty explains that using minerals from mine wastes will be in line with the EU will to reduce dependency from critical imports (Figure 50)
5. Starty explains that the thermoelectric generator materials developed will have desirable properties (Figure 51)
6. Starty explains why recovering waste heat can be important for industry...and to recharge itself! (Figure 52)
7. Starty explains that the START Consortium has all that is needed to carry out the task (Figure 53)
8. Starty shows the START Consortium partners (Figure 54)
9. Starty invites to go to the website and the social media for more info (Figure 55)
10. Starty shows the project website, and the social media where START can be found (Figure 56)
11. A final scene (same as the initial scene)

Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling - A Horizon Europe project

Sustainable energy harvesting systems
based on innovative mine waste recycling

A HORIZON
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Figure 47: The start image of the Introductory Video.

Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling - A Horizon Europe project

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Figure 48: Starty introduces itself.

Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling - A Horizon Europe project

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Figure 49: Starty explains the basic idea behind START, using thermoelectric generators to recover waste heat by using minerals from mine wastes.

Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling - A Horizon Europe project

The thermoelectric materials will be sustainable, coming from EU-sourced ores and re-mined wastes, reducing dependence from outside EU

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Figure 50: Starty explains that using minerals from mine wastes will be in line with the EU will to reduce dependency from critical imports.

Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling - A Horizon Europe project

The thermoelectric properties will be comparable or better than most competing materials

Materials	Bi_2Te_3	PbTe	SiGe	Mg/Si-based materials	Tetrahedrite
Current commercial materials					
Figure of merit (zT)	> 1	> 1	> 1	> 1	> 1
Operational temperature	< 300 °C	< 500 °C	< 900 °C	< 550 °C	< 550 °C
Toxicity	■	■	■	■	■
Environmental aspects	■	■	■	■	■
Raw materials availability	■	■	■	■	■
Large scale manufacture	■	■	■	■	■
Positive assessment ■ Negative assessment ■ Less favourable ■					

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Figure 51: Starty explains that the thermoelectric generator materials developed will have desirable properties.

Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling - A Horizon Europe project

Recovering heat can make industrial processes more efficient, or power off-the-grid electronic devices

Energy efficiency

Co-funded by the European Union

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Figure 52: Starty explains why recovering waste heat can be important for industry...and to recharge itself!

Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling - A Horizon Europe project

The START consortium has all the necessary expertise, from basic science to fabrication of devices

Co-funded by the European Union

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Figure 53: Starty explains that the START Consortium has all that is needed to carry out the task.

Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling - A Horizon Europe project

Co-funded by the European Union

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Figure 54: Starty shows the START Consortium partners.

Figure 55: Starty invites to go to the website and the social media for more info.

Figure 56: Starty shows the project website, and the social media where START can be found.

The video has already been used in some events: for instance, World PM2022 and Raw Materials Week 2022, as detailed elsewhere.

The views are going to be tracked, in order to prove that the KPIs established are achieved.

5.11 CONTINUOUS EVALUATION OF D&C PERFORMANCE

5.11.1 KPIs

KPIs are “a quantifiable measure of performance over time for a specific objective”. Although they are not the same as metrics, in the case of measuring the performance of a website or a social media that is normal.

To assess the dissemination, START will collect metrics from the website, and the social media, and will compare some selected KPIs to chosen reference values that the project expects to meet of the years. A list of the KPIs imagined, with their reference values, is given in Table 3.

Table 3: KPIs considered for D&C activities.

Tool	KPI	Reference value
Project website	Visitors	Year 1: 2000 Year 4: 4000
Twitter	Followers	Year 1: 1000 End: 2500
LinkedIn	Followers	End:800
Videos	Views	More than 100/video Average 200
Newsletters	Addressees	More than 500/issue
Webinars/ seminars/ workshop	Audience	100
Serious online game	Visitors	300
Other publications	Reach	More than 400000

According to previous experiences, as already shown in deliverable D6.1 (“Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools”), an Excel file, named Monitoring Tool for Online Dissemination (MTOD) is used to collect the data of dissemination performance on social media, in order to quantify the audience reached and the interest arisen.

This is located on the START SharePoint (its address is [START/Work Packages/WP6 - Dissemination and communication/START Monitoring Tool for Online Dissemination.xlsx¹³](#)) and contains all the details collected from the different social media posts and contents, and from the website. A preview of the structure of the file is visible in the screenshot of Figure 57.

All partners are asked to enter data there, if they post something related to the project on social media or websites, or via direct mailing to a mailing list. Each item is evaluated in terms of “audience” and of “views”. The former refers to the number of potential contacts, the latter to the feedback on actual clicks, or visualizations, by some contacts in the audience. As an example, the audience for a mailing list is the number of contacts therein, whilst for a LinkedIn page or private account it is the number of followers at the date of the post; views will be the number of contacts that actually open the mail, and for LinkedIn the views reported by LinkedIn’s analytics. The number views are evaluated after a certain period from the post, depending on the media used (after 1 week for direct mailings, 30 days for social media posts, 3 months for YouTube and the website, etc.). The instructions are in a specific sheet in the same file.

The file allows to calculate total audience and views of the actions, and the ratio between views and audience for each action. In this way, during the project course, priorities about the social media could be given.

The data from this file is used to update the Funding & Tender website page on Dissemination (see 5.11.3).

In Figure 57 the present status of the MTOD is shown.

Some data from the table can be compared to the FPIs set before the start of the project. Globally, the KPIs that were to be met already in this first period have actually been met; the number of followers for Twitter and LinkedIn is at the moment low (the former looking more critical than the latter) but it could improve in the next semester, hopefully reaching the targets decided for Year 1.

¹³ Note: this is a private address, not accessible from outside the Consortium.

											Median	215		271.4%		87					
											Average	290		749.1%		9593					
											Total	10157				335753					
What	When	Who	Where	Where2	Views	V_DateMe	V/A	Audience	Notes	End date											
Post on KickOff Meeting	27/06/2022	EPMA	LinkedIn	EPMA Page	1045	18/10/2022	21.3%	4900	Reactions: 16; clicks: 30	27/07/2022											
Post on KickOff Meeting	27/06/2022	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	445	10/08/2022	31.8%	1400	Reactions: 5	27/07/2022											
Post on the Kick-off Meeting	07/07/2022	LPRC	Twitter	START Page	1136	07/11/2022	1646.4%	69	Audience = Engagements + Detail Ex	06/08/2022											
Green Energy Harvesting	26/07/2022	LNEG	Zenodo	START Page	20	04/11/2022			18 downloads	24/10/2022											
Post on START methodology and goals	28/07/2022	LPRC	Twitter	START page	1356	07/11/2022	1558.6%	87	Audience = Engagements + Detail Ex	27/08/2022											
Post on START concept + link to webpage	18/08/2022	LPRC	Twitter	START page	35	07/11/2022	1750.0%	2	Audience = Engagements + Detail Ex	17/09/2022											
Post on KickOff Meeting	09/08/2022	EPMA	LinkedIn	START Page	132	18/10/2022	776.5%	17	Reactions: 9; clicks: 3; reposts: 5	08/09/2022											
Post on START factsheet	26/09/2022	LPRC	Twitter	START page	401	07/11/2022	703.5%	57	Audience = Engagements + Detail Ex	26/10/2022											
Post on World PM2022	04/10/2022	EPMA	LinkedIn	START Page	98	04/11/2022	753.8%	13	Reactions: 2; clicks: 2; reposts: 3	03/11/2022											
Post on World PM2022	04/10/2022	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	150	04/11/2022	10.0%	1500	Reactions: -; clicks: -; reposts: -	03/11/2022											
Post on World PM2022	05/10/2022	LPRC	Twitter	START page	143	07/11/2022	1021.4%	14	Audience = Engagements + Detail Ex	04/11/2022											
Post on World PM2022 End	13/10/2022	EPMA	LinkedIn	START Page	136	14/11/2022	1046.2%	13	Reactions: 5; clicks: 20; reposts: 1	12/11/2022											
Post on World PM2022 End	13/10/2022	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	401	14/11/2022	26.7%	1500	Reactions: 11; clicks: -; reposts: -	12/11/2022											
Post on World PM2022 End	13/10/2022	LPRC	Twitter	START page	145	07/11/2022	690.5%	21	Audience = Engagements + Detail Ex	12/11/2022											
Post on START objectives	21/10/2022	LPRC	Twitter	START page	215	07/11/2022	1075.0%	20	Audience = Engagements + Detail Ex	20/11/2022											
Introductory video	25/10/2022	EPMA	YouTube	START channel	75	15/11/2022	7500.0%	1	Like/Dislike: -/-	23/01/2023											
Post on Introductory video	26/10/2022	EPMA	LinkedIn	START Page	395	14/11/2022	2633.3%	15	Reactions: 17; clicks: 12; reposts: 9	26/11/2022											
Post on Introductory video	26/10/2022	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	305	14/11/2022	20.3%	1500	Reactions: 4; clicks: -; reposts: -	25/11/2022											
Post on Introductory video	27/10/2022	LPRC	Twitter	START page	169	07/11/2022	603.6%	28	Audience = Engagements + Detail Ex	26/11/2022											
Post on World PM2022 Website post	27/10/2022	EPMA	LinkedIn	START Page	318	14/11/2022	2120.0%	15	Reactions: 14; clicks: 13; reposts: 3	26/11/2022											
Post on World PM2022 Website post	27/10/2022	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	459	14/11/2022	30.6%	1500	Reactions: 8; clicks: -; reposts: -	26/11/2022											
Post on EU-LatAm Convention	02/11/2022	EPMA	LinkedIn	START Page	115	14/11/2022	153.3%	75	Reactions: 6; clicks: 3; reposts: 6	02/12/2022											
Post on EU-LatAm Convention	02/11/2022	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	303	14/11/2022	20.2%	1500	Reactions: 4; clicks: -; reposts: -	02/12/2022											
Post on EU-LatAm Convention	02/11/2022	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	EPMA Networking group	158	15/11/2022	4.6%	3414	Reactions: 1; clicks: -; reposts: -	02/12/2022											
Post on EU-LatAm Convention	02/11/2022	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	"Sustainability Professionals" group	35	14/11/2022	0.0%	305705	Reactions: -; clicks: -; reposts: -	02/12/2022											
Post on EU-LatAm Convention	02/11/2022	LPRC	Twitter	START page	260	07/11/2022	464.3%	56	Audience = Engagements + Detail Ex	02/12/2022											
Post on EU-LatAm Convention	03/11/2022	LPRC	Twitter	START page	149	07/11/2022	931.3%	16	Audience = Engagements + Detail Ex	03/12/2022											
Post on EU-LatAm Convention/photos live	03/11/2022	EPMA	LinkedIn	START Page	228	14/11/2022	271.4%	84	Reactions: 16; clicks: 45; reposts: 6	03/12/2022											
Post on EU-LatAm Convention/photos live	03/11/2022	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	280	14/11/2022	18.7%	1500	Reactions: 3; clicks: -; reposts: -	03/12/2022											
Post on EU-LatAm Convention/photos live	04/11/2022	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	EPMA Networking group	306	15/11/2022	9.0%	3414	Reactions: 1; clicks: -; reposts: -	04/12/2022											
Post on EU-LatAm Convention	07/11/2022	LPRC	Twitter	LPRC					Audience = Engagements + Detail Ex	07/12/2022											
Post on Science Week Madrid 22 / Launch	08/11/2022	EPMA	LinkedIn	START Page	298	14/11/2022	292.2%	102	Reactions: 22; clicks: 9; reposts: 7	08/12/2022											
Post on Science Week Madrid 22 / Launch	08/11/2022	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	261	14/11/2022	17.3%	1507	Reactions: 1; clicks: -; reposts: -	08/12/2022											
Post on Science Week Madrid 22 / Launch	08/11/2022	LPRC	Twitter	LPRC					Audience = Engagements + Detail Ex	08/12/2022											
Post on Science Week Madrid 22 / Video	14/11/2022	EPMA	LinkedIn	START Page	9	14/11/2022	7.3%	124	Reactions: -; clicks: -; reposts: -	14/12/2022											
Post on Science Week Madrid 22 / Video	14/11/2022	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	165	14/11/2022	10.9%	1520	Reactions: 1; clicks: -; reposts: -	14/12/2022											
Post on Introductory video	15/11/2022	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	"Thermoelectrics" group		15/11/2022	0.0%	631	Reactions: -; clicks: -; reposts: -	15/12/2022											
Post on Science Week Madrid 22 / Video	15/11/2022	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	EPMA Networking group	11	15/11/2022	0.3%	3433	Reactions: -; clicks: -; reposts: -	15/12/2022											

Figure 57: The Monitoring Tool for Online Dissemination (status on 18/11/2022). In green, data that are considered final (in red, data that are not final but could be finalised as the date is after the expected end date).

5.11.1.1 LinkedIn

For LinkedIn, the number of followers is presently (29/11/2022) is 142 (see also chapter 5.6.2), that is still well below the target of 800 followers at the end of the project, but the time to the end of the project is long and at the moment the people actually contacted is still low (invitations to follow are limited to 100/month per LinkedIn settings). Furthermore, apart from “raise the awareness” posts, the people do not see actual results yet, and the appeal is not so high. So, the distance is not felt critical yet. In Figure 58 a plot of the number of new followers shows that the present figure was basically obtained in the last weeks, where also page views (Figure 59) show a good increase. Reassessment in the next periods will be done to verify if the efforts will be effective or not.

Figure 58: LinkedIn follower metrics.

Figure 59: LinkedIn visitor metrics.

5.11.1.2 Twitter

For Twitter the number of actual followers (currently at 37) is rather low, compared to the planned target for Year 1 of 1000. This can be explained by the lack of project news and activities, which

are planned to expand from year 2 onwards, and also by the recent turmoil regarding Twitter itself as a platform. The number of audiences reached – counting the number of views/impressions, Likes, Retweets, Engagements, Detail Expands, New followers and Profile visits – is, however, interesting (more than 5000 by late November 2022): this number corresponds to real engagement with the project posts, so it can be considered as a more reliable parameter for KPIs assessment.

The figure below shows the increase of the START Twitter activity between 23rd October and 23rd November 2022, boosted by the many events where START was presented to different stakeholders.

Figure 60: Twitter data (last 28 days, consulted on 23/11/2022).

5.11.1.3 Videos

For the videos, we have only one to consider, the introductory video. The publication on Youtube led to 82 views by the date of writing this report (22/11/2022), including those generated by the views on the website, but the posts on LinkedIn sum up to well above 700 views (the actual video views were 700 on 22/11/2022) and on Twitter we can add about 170 views. So, the KPI of at least 100 views, and even the average expected of 200 views, are already exceeded by far.

5.11.1.4 Project website

Concerning the project website, unfortunately the analysis is limited to the data of 30 days (period 17 October – 16 November 2022) because of an erroneous setting of Google Analytics: all data before 17th October have been lost. For that period, the following data have been collected:

- Audience (users, new users, numbers of sessions per user, pageviews, pages/session)
- Acquisition
- Behaviour (visited pages)

The audience data for 1 month look interesting (Figure 61), although a peak in accesses on one day might have been caused by non-human accesses. A further analysis will be done in the next months to assess, in case, more realistic data. As this is the first period where the Google Analytics was working, all visitors appear as new, but a fraction of them is returning more than once. Most of accesses have happened from desktop users.

The target for Year 1, so until 31/05/2023, is 2000 visitors: if all the visits obtained in this analysed month will be confirmed in the next months, even if the first 3 months of the website traffic are not available, the target will be surely achieved. If not, we hope anyway to be able to increase the traffic with the publication of the newsletter and of other materials and news about the project.

Audience				
Period:	17/10/2022	16/11/2022		
Audience	Users	New users	Sessions	Pages/session
Total/average	621	621	675	1.45
New visitors	621	621	621	1.36
Returning visitors	17	0	54	2.52
Sessions				
Sessions/user	1.09			
Page views	980			1.45
Device				
Desktop	591			1.45
Mobile	30			1.52

Figure 61: Google Analytics data for the period 17/10/2022-16/11/2022: Audience.

Concerning the ways to arrive to the website (Figure 62), most of entries happen via direct URL selection in the browser, whereas traffic from social media, searches and referral sites is rather limited. This is something that needs improvement.

Acquisition channels				
Period:	17/10/2022	16/11/2022		
Channel	Users	New users	Sessions	Pages/session
Total/average	621	621	675	1.45
Direct	592	592	633	1.43
Social	17	17	20	1.70
Organic search	10	9	17	1.82
Referral	4	3	5	1.60

Figure 62: Google Analytics data for the period 17/10/2022-16/11/2022: Acquisition channels.

The most visited page is clearly the homepage that is also the usual landing page (Figure 63). The “Contact” page is the second most visited. It is expected that the “Documents” and the “News” pages will have more hits with the publication of the already mentioned material.

Performance of pages				
Period:	17/10/2022	16/11/2022		
Page	Page views	Unique views	Time on page (s)	Arrivals
Total/average	980	877	87.6	675
/	653	611	55.1	598
/contact/	62	52	150.1	34
/the-project/	60	47	65.9	10
/documents/	56	49	233.8	6
/consortium/	55	36	68.7	3
/news/	42	35	153.9	4
/multimedia/	23	19	8.3	0
/news-start-wpm2022/	20	19	44.3	13
/&data=05 01 filipe.nev	2	2	401.0	0
/&data=05 01 filipe.nev	1	1	0.0	1

Figure 63: Google Analytics data for the period 17/10/2022-16/11/2022: Performance of pages.

5.11.1.5 Newsletter

Concerning the newsletter, the distribution through the START mailing list would not be very effective, as the list, including Consortium participants, now comprises only about 80 names, 10 of which come from subscriptions or request of inclusion at events. Nevertheless, EPMA has sent the link to download the Newsletter to about 1600 EPMA member contacts via its weekly E-Mail Newsletter on 29 November, and a new mailing will be done in early December to a list of about 400 non-members. Since the Newsletter was ready only at the end of November 2022, data for downloads or actual views of this issue are not available yet and will be reported in the next deliverable of this series (D6.4). Anyway, especially via the EPMA distribution, the target of 500 has been potentially exceeded by far; clearly it will have to be correlated with the actual downloads recorded.

5.11.2 *WP6 meetings*

To keep track of the activities and their performance, and steer them during the project, the WP6 main partners are called to meet, normally online but in-person meetings are also possible. These include:

- the WP6 leader (EPMA)
- the other WP6 task leader (ASGMI)
- the other partner responsible for social media accounts (LPRC)
- the coordinator (LNEG)
- the leaders of WPs, i.e., the components of the ExCom
- specific partners that will be invited if their participation will be useful in the discussion, for instance if their activity is required in the following months.

As per the DCP, the meetings will be at least 2 per semester; with EPMA taking care of preparing the minutes and distributing them to participants, in addition to uploading them to the SharePoint

under WP6/Meetings. Other smaller group meetings may be called for specific discussions, like the detailed organisation of a particular event where only some partners are involved.

In the first semester, the WP6 had the following conference calls:

- WP6 Meeting 01: 11 July, 11:00-12:30
- WP6 Meeting 02: 01 August, 11:30-13:00
- 10 November, 11:00-12:00 (EPMA-LNEG-ASGMI-IGME)

The relevant minutes are available on the project's SharePoint.

5.11.3 Continuous reporting on Funding&Tender website

The WP Leader (EPMA) is responsible of regularly updating the information on Dissemination and Communication in the relevant section in the project's Continuous Reporting on the Funding&Tender website. There are four pages dedicated to these topics on the portal: "Publications", "Dissemination", "Communication" and "Events and training".

At the latest, an update must be made before the end of each reporting period, as at each periodic report, all the information present in the Continuous Reporting section will be automatically compiled to create Part A of the Periodic Technical Report.

For the moment, only the Publications page has been updated (Figure 64): the 3 publications uploaded on the Zenodo platform have been reported.

The screenshot shows the 'Publications' page on the Funding&Tender portal. The page has a navigation bar with tabs for 'Project Summary', 'Researchers involved in the project', 'Deliverables', 'Milestones', 'Critical Risks', 'Publications', 'Results', 'Dissemination activities', 'Standards', 'Patents (IP)', 'Communication activities', 'Datasets', 'Events and training', 'Dissemination', 'Impact', 'Impact Candidates', and 'Other Results'. The 'Publications' tab is active, and it shows a table of project publications. The table has columns for 'Type', 'Title', 'Authors', 'Title of the Journal or equivalent', 'Number', 'Peer-reviewed', 'Was the publication available in open access through the repository at the time of publication', 'PID (Publisher version of record)', 'PID of deposited publication', and 'Action'. There are three rows of data in the table.

Type	Title	Authors	Title of the Journal or equivalent	Number	Peer-reviewed	Was the publication available in open access through the repository at the time of publication	PID (Publisher version of record)	PID of deposited publication	Action
1	Publication in conference procees	Presentation of the START project	de Oliveira, Daniel		False	False			
2	Other	GREEN ENERGY HARVESTING - START project	START project		False	True			
3	Other	Presentation of the START project	Noves, C		False	False			

Figure 64: Screenshot of the page dedicated to Publications on the Funding&Tender portal.

The "Dissemination", "Communication" and "Events and training" pages will be updated later.

6 TASK 6.2: TECHNICAL AND SCIENTIFIC DISSEMINATION

Task leader: EPMA; Participants: All; M01 to M48

All partners will submit papers in relevant conferences, congresses, exhibitions, and scientific journals to give information on the results of the START project.

- Relevant EPMA events (for the PM community mainly):
 - The EuroPM and/or WorldPM Congress and Exhibition series (a project booth is foreseen)
 - The EPMA technical seminars by sectors (Functional Materials, Hot Isostatic Pressing, etc.)
 - Sectoral Group meetings, e.g.:
 - European Functional Materials Sectoral Group (EuroFM)
 - European Hot Isostatic Pressing Sectoral Group (EuroHIP)
 - Environment, Health, Quality and Safety Working Group (EHQS).
- International Conference on Thermoelectrics (ICT/ECT/ACT conference series), and other conferences to be defined by the consortium.
- Special dissemination seminars and presentations (webinars or in person) on specific project-related topics:
 - contributions from the consortium
 - selected external speakers
 - ads on dedicated printed or online magazines (e.g., Journal of Degraded and Mining Lands Management, Journal of Environmental Management, Environmental Earth Sciences, Environmental Science and Pollution Research, Mine Water and the Environment...)

External events to communicate to the public and to other scientific and industrial communities and improve the awareness of the energy and sustainability issues in the public: EPMA and other consortium partners will take part in

- At least 2 external events and exhibitions per year
- Possibly Science Festivals and Fairs (e.g., the European Researchers' Night) to communicate the scope of the project and improve the awareness of the energy and sustainability issues in the public.

Specific KPIs will be introduced to quantify the impact of project dissemination.

Publications and presentations in conferences, seminars and congresses are strongly encouraged: all consortium partners should try to organise a technical participation in an event to disseminate a part of the work carried out in START. This will broaden the audience for the project topics and in the end will create the condition for successful exploitation.

Thus, maybe with some exceptions, we expect that during the course of the project almost all partners will submit papers in relevant conferences, congresses, exhibitions, and scientific journals to give information on the results of the START project.

Addressing communities that are outside those already covered by the consortium members activities and by the standard journals, magazines and conferences/events is also rather important for an innovative project like START. For this reason, the plan is to try addressing external

communities by publishing well balanced papers and articles in more general magazines, or news services/websites (the Horizon Results, the Horizon Magazine, also suitable generic magazines, like for instance the Open Access Government magazine).

6.1 EVENTS LIST

In order to select the events where the partners, individually or as consortium, should take part, and take materials concerning the project, a **“START Events List”** is established and regularly updated by the WP6 leader (EPMA) on the START SharePoint and every partner will collaborate by giving information on possible events.

In this Excel file, the following information is collected for each event:

- Name of Event
- Priority: the partners are asked to evaluate what is the priority to give to this event in order to try maximising the impact by optimising the effort.
- Date of start of event
- Date of end of event
- Physical/Online/Hybrid: if available, information on the type of participation requested.
- Website: where possible, the link to obtain fresh info about the event
- Location: where the event will be held (in case, “online”)
- Type of audience: scientific (what sector), industrial (what sector), general (what composition) etc.
- START Booth: whether a START booth should be present at the event
- Partner Booth: whether a START partner booth should be present at the event (including name of partner)
- START lectures/papers: in case a presentation is given, details on the topic (e.g., “Generic project presentation” or a specific topic)
- START lecture/paper date: when the presentation will happen
- Presenter: who is going to present
- Reference partner: the partner who will be coordinating the participation
- Attendees: expected number of attendees

The list is the basis for discussion, in the meetings, about participation at the various events.

In Figure 65 the present status of the list is shown.

Event	Priority (1=high)	Date start	Date end	Physical /Online/ Hybrid	Website	Location	Type of audience	START Booth	Partner Booth	START lectures/papers	START lecture/paper date	Presenter	Reference partner	A
EIT Raw Materials Summit (every year around April/May)	-	2022, May		Physical	https://www.eitrawsummit.com/									
EGU - European Geoscience Union (every year around April/May)	-	2022, May		Physical	https://www.egu.eu/									
PDAC - Prospectors & Developers Association of Canada	-	2022, Jun		Physical	https://www.pdac.ca/									
Sustainable Minerals '22	1.50	11/07/2022	13/07/2022	Online	https://mei.eventsair.com/sustainable-minerals-22/									
1st Scientific-Technical Conference of the Geological and Mining Institute of Spain - National center	1.00	12/07/2022	13/07/2022	Physical	https://www.igme.es/PagNicio2014/fotos/	Madrid (Spain)	IGME-CISC Internal			presentation		E. Boixereu i Vila	IGME-CSIC	
Desafios para la gestion sostenible de los pasivos ambientales mineros/ ECLAC-CEPAL United Nations	1.00	01/08/2022	04/08/2022	Physical	https://www.cepal.org/es/eventos/evento	Perú	Mining companies, Geological Surveys, academia, SI			presentation		Freddy Guzman, Ch	ASGMI	
The Ceramics Expo 2022	1.00	29/08/2022	31/08/2022	Physical	https://www.ceramicsexpousa.com/	Huntington Convention Center of Cleveland, Ohio (USA)	PM community	-	GeniCore					
International Materials, Applications and Technologies (IMAT) - ASM 2022	1.00	12/09/2022	15/09/2022	Physical	https://www.asminternational.org/web/im	New Orleans, Louisiana (USA)	PM community, Academic	-	GeniCore			Damian Karpowicz		
European Conference on Thermoelectrics (ECT) 2022	2.00	14/09/2022	16/09/2022	Physical	https://www.ect2022barcelona.org	Barcelona (Spain)	Thermoelectric Academic			to be considered for the following years				
Perumin 35 mining convention	1.00	26/09/2022	30/09/2022	Physical	https://perumin.com	Arequipa (Peru)	Mining companies, Geological Surveys, academia, SI			banner at the EC booth				ASGMI
WorldPM22	1.00	09/10/2022	13/10/2022	Physical	https://www.worldpm2022.com/	Lyon (France)	PM community	Yes	-	EuroFM sectoral Group meeting	11/12/2022	F. Neves	EPMA	
WorldPM22	1.00	09/10/2022	13/10/2022	Physical	https://www.worldpm2022.com/	Lyon (France)	PM community	Yes	-	Industry Corner	11/12/2022	F. Neves	EPMA	
WorldPM22	1.00	09/10/2022	13/10/2022	Physical	https://www.worldpm2022.com/	Lyon (France)	PM community	-	GeniCore	Booth				
WorldPM22	1.00	09/10/2022	13/10/2022	Physical	https://www.worldpm2022.com/	Lyon (France)	PM community	-	MBN	Booth				
IV EDITION MMH, Sustainable Mining	-	18/10/2022	20/10/2022	Physical	https://mmhseville.com/mineria-sostenible	Sevilla (Spain)	Mining					D. de Oliveira	CSIC	
EU-Latin America convention	1.00	03/11/2022	04/11/2022	Physical	https://www.mineralplatform.eu/events/eu-latin-america-convention-raw-materials					Presentation		D. de Oliveira	ASGMI	
EU-Latin America policy dialogue on the identification of strategic and critical Raw Materials resources	1.00	02/11/2022	03/11/2022	Physical	https://www.mineralplatform.eu/events/eu-latin-america-convention-raw-materials							D. de Oliveira	ASGMI	
Raw Materials Week 2022 (every year in November)	1.00	14/11/2022	18/11/2022	Physical	https://www.eurawmaterialsweek.eu/2022	Brussels (Belgium)	Raw materials/mining			poster, video				LPRC, SINTEF
II Extraordinary General Assembly of ASGMI	1.00	14/11/2022	18/11/2022	Physical		Barcelona (Spain)	Geological Surveys Directors			banner, video				ASGMI
1st START Webinar (LNEG)	1.00	2023, Feb		Online	START website	-		-	-	Project pres		F. Neves	LNEG	
1st START Webinar (LNEG)	1.00	2023, Feb		Online	START website	-		-	-	Technical pres		Many	LNEG	
GENERA 2023 (international Energy and Environment Fair)	1.00	21/02/2023	23/02/2023	Physical	https://www.ifema.es/en/genera	Madrid	Energy and Environment							
Amniera	1.67	22/05/2023	24/05/2023	Physical		Buenos Aires (Argentina)	Energy, Transport & logistic, Mining Technology and industrial fairs							ASGMI
Jornadas Científico Técnicas del IGME-CSIC	1.00	2023, Jun?			www.csic.es							Ester Boixereu	IGME	
Euronanoforum2023	1.67	11/06/2023	13/06/2023	Physical	https://mkon.nu/euro_nano_forum_2023	Malmö (Sweden)								

Figure 65: Status of the START Events List Excel file (updated 18/11/2022) for the initial part of the project. In light green the events covered.

The tool will be used all along the project, by updating the lines (the upcoming events) and reassessing the priorities continuously. In this beginning stage, some upcoming events have been provisionally assigned high priority, whereas others, for which the consortium was not ready with the materials have been deprioritised, but in the case of recurring events they will be reconsidered for 2023 and successive years. Some high priority recurring events are these:

- European Conference on Thermoelectrics (ECT) conference series
- GENERA (International Energy and Environment Fair)
- Raw Materials Week
- EIT Raw Materials summit
- EU-Latin America partnership on Raw Materials
- EU Green week
- EPMA's EuroPM Powder Metallurgy yearly Congress & Exhibition (WorldPM in 2022)
- EPMA's seminars (HIP, Functional Materials)
- Sustainable Minerals
- In general, when partners have large internal events, these will be covered.

6.2 EVENTS COVERED IN M01-M06

Despite the fact that the start of the activities only happened in last June, so not many technical advances have been possible until now, the consortium is keen on disseminating about the project. Clearly, in this initial phase every dissemination is just to raise the awareness about the project and the topics linked to it, like recovering waste heat, thermoelectric materials and devices, reminding mine wastes to reduce materials dependence from overseas. So, it is mostly communication, as there are no results conveyed yet, although the target was, mainly, in the scientific and industrial community, and only partially stakeholders at other levels, including the general public.

During the last weeks, many were already the events where START featured, one way or another, in Europe but also outside of Europe, beginning in M02 (July 2022), just a few weeks after the KoM. Here is a short report for each of them.

6.2.1 1st Scientific-Technical Conference of the Geological and Mining Institute of Spain – National Center, Madrid (Spain), 12th-13th July 2022

E. Boixereu i Vila of IGME-CSIC presented the START project at this event, which was hosted in the IGME headquarters in Tres Cantos, Madrid, Spain, in mid-July. The poster shown is visible in Figure 39.

Figure 66: Presentation of START at the 1st ICME-CSIC conference.

The proceedings of the event are available^{14,15}, where a page on START is included.

6.2.2 CEPAL Regional Event, Miraflores (Peru), 1st-4th Aug 2022

The ASGMI MELs Expert Group Chair, F Guzman, participated on the event organized by CEPAL (Comisión Económica para América Latina, or Economic Commission for Latin America, one of five regional commissions of the UN, based in Santiago

de Chile¹⁶) and named “Challenges for sustainable management of Mining Environmental Liabilities (MELs)”. The event took place in Miraflores, Peru from 1st-4th August 2022¹⁷.

Figure 67: A moment of the CEPAL Regional Event.

In his presentation “Gestión sostenible de los Pasivos Ambientales Mineros: Enfoque en Iberoamérica”, held on 1st August 11:15-11:35, F. Guzman talked about challenges for the

¹⁴ <https://digital.csic.es/handle/10261/281251>

¹⁵ <https://zenodo.org/record/7092555#.Y2O5R-TMKHs>, page 100

¹⁶ <https://www.cepal.org/en/about>

¹⁷ <https://www.cepal.org/es/eventos/evento-regional-desafios-la-gestion-sostenible-pasivos-ambientales-mineros>, in Spanish

sustainable management of mining liabilities. He explained the activity of the ASGMI Expert Group in Mining Liabilities, he presented the methodological documents and guides that the Group has already published and that they are working on at the moment, and he talked with a few slides about the START Project (general description and objectives) in which experts of the Group are going to participate as experts in sampling methodology.

6.2.3 Perumin 2022, Arequipa (Peru), 26th-30th Sep 2022

Perumin¹⁸ is one the largest and most relevant mining conventions in Latin America (+60.000 participants, +1,400 stands and 29,000 m2). Its 2022 edition took place on September 26-30 at the Cerro Juli Convention Center, located in the city of Arequipa (Peru).

Under the umbrella of the EC stand of the Mineral Development Network Platform and thanks to the link to the EU project “Eu-Latin America partnership on raw materials”¹⁹, START was selected as relevant EU project and was promoted at the stand with a specifically generated banner. It was a key event for the promotion of START thanks to the enormous audience and being under the umbrella of the EC stand reinforced the project appeal.

Figure 68: A moment of Perumin 2022.

¹⁸ <https://perumin.com/perumin35/public/en>

¹⁹ <https://www.mineralplatform.eu/about/the-platform/background>

6.2.4 International Workshop in Geochemistry, Medellín (Colombia), 19th-23rd Sep 2022

The hybrid Workshop "Geochemical Information for Society"²⁰ organized by ASGMI and the Colombian Geological Service was held on 19th-23rd September 2022.

The objectives of the workshop were to present the manual of procedures and methodologies for taking and preparing geochemical samples, prepared by the ASGMI Group of Experts in Geochemistry -GEGEOQ-, and to have an overview of the state of the art of geochemistry in Ibero-American countries and learn about the experiences of other Geochemistry

Groups, such as those of IUGS, UNESCO and EuroGeoSurveys.

G. Olivenza of ASGMI gave a general presentation about the activities the activities of expert groups and projects in which they are participating; among them the START Project, with a brief description.

6.2.5 World PM2022, Lyon (France), 9th-13th Oct 2022

World PM 2022²¹ is a world event on Powder Metallurgy organized by EPMA (every 6 years the European association organizes the world congress). It always includes a congress and an exhibition. The event was hosted at the Congress Centre in Lyon (France), 9th-13th October: about 1100 participants

both from industry and academia took part in the event, a significant figure given the fact the two previous editions (European congresses) had to be run online because of the pandemic, the last physical edition being the event Euro PM2019 in Maastricht (NL).

EPMA prepared a 3m x 3m booth for the project that was decorated with posters, roller banners, leaflets, a set of significant samples in a showcase with explicative labels, and a screen with a rolling video presenting the project for the whole duration of the exhibition. EPMA personnel covered the exhibition time as much as possible.

²⁰ <https://asgmi.org/taller-informacion-geoquimica-para-la-sociedad-19-23-septiembre-medellin/>

²¹ www.worldp2022.com

Figure 69: START booth at World PM 2022.

Figure 70: Some partners of START in the START booth at World PM2022.

The coordinator Filipe Neves of LNEG was invited to give two presentations:

- Industry Corner: 30' presentation slot in the Exhibition area. Title: “Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling” Speaker F. Neves. Tuesday 11/10/2022, 13:15-13:45.
- EuroFM Sectoral Group Meeting: Title “The START project”. F. Neves was invited to present during the open meeting of the EPMA Sectoral Group on Functional Materials on Tuesday 11/10/2022, 17:00-18:30.

Figure 71: F. Neves during his presentation in the EuroFM Sectoral Group meeting.

The Technical Managers of EPMA, B. Vicenzi and K. Boz, mentioned START in all their presentations during the so-called Sectoral Group meetings (6 meetings and presentations overall, 30-40 participants in every meeting).

Two other consortium companies were exhibiting in the event: Genicore and MBN.

The agenda is too large to be reported here but can be found in the Congress website²². At page 69, an ad about START has been included in the technical guide.

As PM is one of the key technologies for START, participation was useful to raise the awareness in the PM community about these materials and application, and to start a networking activity for the project.

²² <https://www.worldpm2022.com/technical-programme/>

6.2.6 *EU-Latin America RM Convention, and EU-Latin America policy dialogue on the identification of strategic and critical Raw Materials resources, Santiago de Chile, 2nd-4th Nov 2022*

The 2022 EU-Latin America Convention on Raw Materials²³ took place on 3rd and 4th November in Santiago, Chile and bringing together the mineral raw materials value chain

community, including policymakers, industry, the private sector, and research and innovation actors, from the EU and Latin America under the following overarching theme: Mineral Raw Materials for the Clean Energy Transition. The Convention included a high-level (political) session on day 1, and panel sessions on days 1 and 2.

On Friday 4th November, during the 11:30 – 12:30 Panel session “Downstream raw materials for the energy transition – refining, battery manufacturing & recycling”, D. de Oliveira (LNEG) presented with the title “START project” the details of our project.

In connection with this convention, the “EU-Latin America policy dialogue on the identification of strategic and critical Raw Materials resources” meeting took place (2nd-3rd November). This activity brings together Geological Surveys from EU and Latin America together with key national and international organisations.

The dialogue focused on the analysis of strategic and critical raw materials necessary for the clean energy and digital transition. The result of this dialogue will be a roadmap for the elaboration of the Critical and Strategic Raw Materials map in Latin America together with the Communication and Dissemination Strategy.

The coordinator of the Mining Liabilities Expert Group, F. Guzman, participated in this physical meeting with a presentation of the group activities and also of the START project.

²³ <https://www.mineralplatform.eu/events/eu-latin-america-convention-raw-materials-2022>

Figure 72: The START roller banner at the EU-Latin America Convention 2022.

Figure 73: The START participants with the roller banner at the EU-Latin America Convention 2022.

Figure 74: The START leaflets for distribution at the EU-Latin America Convention 2022.

6.2.7 Science and Innovation Week, Madrid (Spain), 10TH Nov 2022

On 10th November, 18:00-20:00, E. Boixereu I Vila (IGME-CSIC) gave a presentation²⁴ in Spanish on the START project at the headquarters of the

professional association of Spanish geologists (ICOG), in Madrid (Figure 75). The conference was part of an event called Semana de la Ciencia y la Innovación (Science and Innovation Week)²⁵ in Madrid. This week “is an event for scientific dissemination and citizen participation organized by the Community of Madrid through the Foundation for Knowledge Madrid whose objective is to actively involve society in research processes and development in science, technology and innovation”, and is aimed at the general public. The conference, whose title in English would be “How to generate electricity from mining tailings”, was also broadcasted online on Goto.com and recorded (Figure 76) and is available for rewatch on YouTube²⁶. 118 people have watched the video so far.

OFFICIAL COLLEGE OF GEOLOGISTS

Como generar electricidad a partir de las escombreras mineras

Figure 75: E. Boixereu I Vila during the presentation at the Semana de la Ciencia y la Innovación, Madrid.

²⁴ <https://cgeologos.es/evento/como-generar-electricidad-a-partir-de-las-escombreras-mineras>

²⁵ <https://www.semanacienciamadrid.org/>

²⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=exlpVN2MVVY>

Figure 76: A screenshot taken during the presentation at the Semana de la Ciencia y la Innovación, Madrid.

6.2.8 Raw Materials Week, Brussels (Belgium), 14th-18th Nov 2022

The seventh edition of the "Raw Materials Week"²⁷ took place from 14th to 18th November 2022 as physical and hybrid, gathering a wide range of stakeholders discussing policies and initiatives in the field of raw materials. The programme included the ninth annual High-level Conference of the European Innovation Partnership (EIP)

on raw materials and several complementary events on Critical Raw Materials, Trends in innovation and Skills for raw materials, EU-Ukraine strategic partnership on raw materials and batteries, EU Horizon technology success stories, EU-Canada Partnership, UNECE Resource management.

Some members of the consortium took part in selected days and sessions, in person (LPRC and SINTEF) and online, with some turnout in terms of networking, as the participants were estimated to be between 200 and 300 per day, so probably more than 300 unique participants for the whole event. The introductory video and a poster of the project (Figure 42) were shown during the breaks on screen (Figure 77, Figure 78) and in streaming during hybrid events (Figure 79, Figure 80), and were also available on the media page of the event (Figure 81 and Figure 82).

²⁷ <https://www.eurawmaterialsweek.eu/2022>

Figure 77: The START poster showed during breaks in the Raw Materials Week events.

Figure 78: The START introductory video showed during breaks in the Raw Materials Week events.

Figure 79: The START poster showed during breaks in the Raw Materials Week events (here, in the streaming of the 9th Annual High-Level Conference of the European Innovation Partnership (EIP) on raw materials, including EU-Ukraine strategic partnership on raw materials and batteries, 16/11/2022, hybrid).

Figure 80: The START video showed during breaks in the Raw Materials Week events (here, in the streaming of the 9th Annual High-Level Conference of the European Innovation Partnership (EIP) on raw materials, including EU-Ukraine strategic partnership on raw materials and batteries, 16/11/2022, hybrid).

Figure 81: Gallery page of Raw Materials Week 2022, showing START.

Raw Materials Week 2022

Home Replay Agenda Speakers Satellite Events Gallery Profile Logout

Gallery

Poster

START

START - Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling

Primary objective: Build an European innovation ecosystem for thermoelectric (TE) waste heat harvesting systems.

How: By incorporating sulphides (tetrahedrite), present in many European mine wastes, into advanced sulphide p-type TE materials.

Expected impact towards a more sustainable and resilient EU:

- Reducing EU dependence on primary critical raw materials
- Promotion of circular economy processes
- Efficiency of energy production and consumption systems, with reduction of fossil fuels consumption and greenhouse gas emissions.

SCHEMATICS OF A THERMOELECTRICAL MODULE START CONCEPT

www.START-HEproject.com

Co-funded by the European Union

Organised by European Commission

Video

START Introductory Video - Starty tells you the basics!

The thermoelectric materials will be sustainable, coming from EU-sourced ores and re-mined wastes, reducing dependence on outside EU

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Figure 82: The page dedicated to START in the Raw Materials Week 2022 Gallery section.

6.2.9 II Extraordinary General Assembly of ASGMI, Barcelona (Spain), 14th-18th Nov 2022

From 14th to 18th November, the II Extraordinary General Assembly of ASGMI was held in Barcelona (Spain). Besides the Board of Directors meeting in

which are discussed management and administration issues, an International Workshop was celebrated on “The Role of Geological Surveys in the territorial planning and management”, featuring the participation of the ASGMI Geological Surveys associated but also the participation of international organizations such as the EuroGeoSurveys, Geological Survey of Canada and United States, and the Organization of Africans Geological Surveys.

On 17th November, one of the presentations in the event, the Annual Report of Activities of the ASGMI Expert Groups, mentioned project START and showed the promotional video of the project, since two of ASGMI expert group (mineral resources and mining environmental liabilities) are participating in the project.

Figure 83: ASGMI General Assembly (Nov 2022).

Figure 84: ASGMI General Assembly (Nov 2022).

Figure 85: START video being shown in the ASGMI General Assembly (Nov 2022).

6.3 EVENTS IN PREPARATION

START will surely take part in more events in the upcoming months. In particular, we are looking forward to the GENERA 2023²⁸ (International Energy and Environment Fair), that will take place in Madrid on 21st-23rd February 2023.

We are also planning to run a free webinar, probably also in February 2023. The date, title and content have not been planned yet.

6.4 PUBLICATIONS

For the moment, a few documents have been produced for publication:

- A short document (3 pages) made available also on the project's website, and also hosted in SlideShare, that is titled "Green energy harvesting - State of the art"²⁹. It was prepared by LNEG in July 2022.
- A 22-pages pdf of the presentation given by F. Neves (LNEG), START coordinator, at the EPMA World PM2022 Powder Metallurgy World Congress and Exhibition in October 2022³⁰.
- A 21-pages pdf of the presentation given by D. de Oliveira (LNEG), at the EU-Latin America Partnership on Raw Materials in November 2022³¹.
- The 11-pages pdf of Issue 1 of the START Newsletter "RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE"¹²

Zenodo is used as the START default open access repository. In Zenodo, a DOI is automatically assigned to each uploaded data, as explained in deliverable D1.3 (Data Management Plan). A

²⁸ <https://www.ifema.es/en/genera>

²⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6906481>

³⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7326411>

³¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7327407>

“community” named “Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling”, that is the extended title for START, was created (Figure 86). In this page, the mentioned documents have been uploaded, making them again publicly available, with the addition, compared to SlideShare, that a DOI has been obtained for each, and they have automatically been added in the Continuous Reporting Publications page in the Funding & Tender portal for the project (see chapter 5.11.3).

An example is the document on “Green Energy Harvesting – State of the Art” that was also uploaded to the website (more details are available in chapter 6.4).

zenodo Search [] Upload Communities Log in Sign up

Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling

Recent uploads

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November 4, 2022 (v1) Presentation Open Access View

Presentation of the START project at the 2022 EU-Latin America Convention on Raw Materials

de Oliveira, Daniel;

This document consists of the presentation of the START project carried out at the 2022 EU-Latin America Convention on Raw Material (3-4 November, Santiago, Chile) during the Panel session "Downstream raw materials for the energy transition – refining, battery ma

Uploaded on November 16, 2022

October 11, 2022 (v1) Presentation Open Access View

Presentation of the START project at the World PM2022 Congress & Exhibition

Neves, F.;

This document combines the two presentations of the project START made at the Industry Corner and at the European Functional Materials Group (EuroFM) meeting during the World PM2022 Congress & Exhibition (9-13 October 2022, Lyon, France). The document provides a comprehensive summary o

Uploaded on November 16, 2022

July 26, 2022 (v1) Technical note Open Access View

GREEN ENERGY HARVESTING - STATE OF THE ART

START project.

In this publication it is given a brief overview on the state of art of green energy harvesting. Green energy harvesting aims to supply electricity to electric or electronic systems from an energy source present in the environment (e.g., thermal energy (thermoelectricity)) without grid connect

Uploaded on July 26, 2022

More

New upload

Community

START

Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling

This community collects all types of open access publications generated in the **START project**, including publications in journals and conferences, deliverables and newsletters, as well as other published materials. **START**, which stands for **Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling** is an innovation action project supported by the European Union and its Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No. 101058632.

For more information, please visit the **START website** at [START PROJECT – Official Website \(start-heproject.com\)](#)

Disclaimer: Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Curated by:
FNeves

Curation policy:
New uploads by START project members will be accepted in this community.

Created:
July 25, 2022

Harvesting API:
[OAI-PMH interface](#)

Want your upload to appear in this community?

- Click the button above to upload a record directly to this community. To add one of your existing records to the community, edit the record, add this community under the "Communities" section, save, and finally publish.
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Figure 86: The Zenodo page for the START community “Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling”.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo interface for a document titled "GREEN ENERGY HARVESTING - STATE OF THE ART". The document is categorized as a "Technical note" and is "Open Access". It was published on July 26, 2022, and has 19 views and 16 downloads. The document is indexed in OpenAIRE. The publication date is July 26, 2022, with a DOI of 10.5281/zenodo.6906481. The keyword(s) are "GREEN ENERGY HARVESTING" and "Thermoelectric waste heat". The grant(s) listed is the "European Commission" grant "START - SUSTAINABLE ENERGY HARVESTING SYSTEMS BASED ON INNOVATIVE MINE WASTE RECYCLING (101058632)". The license is Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. The document is available as a PDF file (408.3 kB). The page also shows a "Citations" section with a search bar and a "Share" section with social media icons. The footer includes navigation links, funding logos (CERN, OpenAIRE, European Union), and a footer bar with "Powered by CERN Data Centre & Invenio" and "Status Privacy policy Terms of Use Support".

Figure 87: The Zenodo page for the START document “Green energy harvesting – State of the art”.

Figure 88 A screenshot of the Zenodo version of the document “Green energy harvesting – State of the art” – July 2022.

Figure 89: A screenshot of the Zenodo page for the document “Presentation of the START project at the World PM2022 Congress & Exhibition” – October 2022.

A publication on an industry sector magazine is being planned already for the spring 2023. After a contact obtained at the event World PM2022, the editors of the magazine “Powder Metallurgy Review”³² have offered to publish an article outlining the START project, its origins/inspiration, its aims, and its achievements to date, with a minimum 2000 words and at least 7 accompanying images. The Powder Metallurgy Review is published quarterly in print and digital formats, distributed upon subscription, e-newsletters and dedicated social media networks (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn), at numerous industry events worldwide (already imagined RAPID in Chicago, as well as a number of other spring events still to be confirmed), and indefinitely available on the magazine website. The target is clearly the powder metallurgy community, thus within groups 2 and 3 in our target segmentation (component manufacturers, end-users, industry suppliers, analysts, researchers), with possible outreach also in groups 1 and 4 because of the free web visibility. According to the publisher, the average circulation per issue of Powder Metallurgy Review over the last year is well above 10000, mostly as online/pdf.

The text will have to be ready by mid-January 2023.

Figure 90: The latest issue cover (Autumn 2022, 120 pages) of the Powder Metallurgy Review printed and web magazine, that will host an article on START in its Spring 2023 issue.

No further publication has been planned yet, but there will be others in the next months, especially as scientific data will be available in the later stages of the project, and other presentations will be given in other events leading to publications.

³² <https://www.pm-review.com/>

7 TASK 6.3: TRAINING ACTIVITIES

Task leader: EPMA; Participants: All; M12 to M48

This task aims to ensure the transfer of high-value knowledge present within partners and generated by the project to promote learning opportunities and building capacities with and for young scientists. We will make use of established and new training activities, to funnel knowledge to students, young engineers, and experts:

- A strategic document on how to present, promote, call, recruit and orient and mentoring young students and researchers into the project
- Project lectures during the EPMA PM Summer School³³. During the 4 years of the project, we plan to reach at least 200 students by this activity (normally 50-60 participants in each edition). This includes the preparation of a lecture, updated every year, about START activities. A quick information about START – one slide - was already given by B. Vicenzi (EPMA) during his initial address to the attendees (58 plus the speakers and the local organizers) in the 2022 edition of the Summer School, that was held from 20th to 24th June in Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha in Ciudad Real (Spain) (Figure 91, Figure 92).
- ASGMI has significant experience working with Mining Environmental Liabilities. In the past, several workshops and events have been organized on this topic³⁴. ASGMI will develop learning material based on the already existing products & experience and will add new information and results from START (mainly from WP 2). The objective is to hold a free online seminar open to bachelor and master's degree young students where they can interact with the researchers, ask questions and learn details of the project.
- During a final Training Workshop for scientists and industry members, focused on sustainability of the developed know-how. Lecturers from the consortium will give presentation to external participants.

This task is not active yet but will start in the next semester. Nothing else to report.

³³ <https://summerschool.epma.com/>

³⁴ <https://asgmi.org/grupo-de-expertos-en-pasivosambientales-mineros-2/>

8 TASK 6.4: CLUSTERING

Task leader: ASGMI; Participants: All; M03 to M48

The objective of the clustering activity, that constitutes task T6.4 and began at M03 and will continue for the whole project duration to end at M48, is building a comprehensive cluster for the dissemination of the project. The main idea is to create an effective strategy to identify similar and interesting projects and find synergies to create value, avoid duplications and strengthen and maximize the START project results impact.

Projects that share a common theme or address similar challenges can form a cluster initiative and deliver shared strategic outputs. Thus, START wants to enhance links and synergies with such projects and initiatives. ASGMI with the support of all partners is identifying the project coordinators of the selected projects & initiatives. Mapping the synergies among the different projects will maximize the impact and contribute to have a more efficient and strong European Innovation. As a first point a database contenting interesting project and initiatives is being created. Different resources will feed this database, such as:

- the Community Research and Development Information Service (CORDIS) for H2020 or Horizon Europe projects
- the EIT (including the KICs on Raw Materials, InnoEnergy & Climate KIC)
- the internal community (partners in the consortium and its members)

The link will be normally established by a series of online short meetings with the relevant Project Coordinators or key people and the START project coordinator and/or the Communication WP leader. Key events and meetings will be also essential to identify and establish good connections: the people from the initiatives in the clustering database, likely belonging to the audience target Groups 2 and 3, but hopefully in some cases also from Group 1, will be invited to the relevant events organized by START (seminars, webinars, trainings, final event) ensuring dedicated time for networking and collaboration. Conversely, START consortium members participating to events are supposed to seek connections with all interesting stakeholders.

8.1 CLUSTERING STRATEGY

A clustering strategy has been designed in order to be implemented during the whole project duration. This strategy consists of two work lines: internal and external clustering:

8.1.1 *Internal clustering*

Consortium members are going to be contacted to identify projects, or other initiatives in which they are involved and/or are aware of, and check if they have common points and potential to establish synergies.

8.1.2 *External clustering*

The strategy for external clustering consists in contacting institutions and organizations that are not directly involved in the START project but work in similar or complementary themes. These can be classified as explained in the next subchapters.

8.1.2.1 Key institutions and actors

Associations and big organizations directly or indirectly related to technical projects or other research initiatives are especially important because networks in which they are involved have a big potential for clustering with START project. They have a “helicopter view” of the activities done by their members and contacting them is a fast and easy way to reach a large number of potential projects.

Key people (outreach people and project leaders) in these organizations have been identified and contacted in order to schedule meetings between projects or work package leaders.

Clustering task and communication leaders of the project have already contacted key people in EIT Raw Materials and InnoEnergy KICs, and EuroGeoSurveys.

Some initial meetings have already taken place.

8.1.2.2 Link with communication and dissemination activities

Project consortium members participation in technical or commercial big events, congress u other initiatives is interesting because this participation brings the opportunity to meet key people and find out new projects or initiatives related directly or indirectly with the project in order to stablish synergies.

To maximize the potential of clustering in these events, clustering strategy consist of build a list of the events in which the consortium members are going to attend, identify potential organizations or key participants in the event and suggest to the consortium members to contact them before and during the events to talk about related projects.

8.1.2.3 CORDIS

CORDIS provides information on all EU-supported R&D activities, including programs (H2020, FP7 and older), projects, results and publications so is an essential platform for looking for projects under same or similar calls and finding out the coordinator to establish contact.

8.1.2.4 Data base creation

A database has been created to list the clustering actions (see chapter 8.1.3).

This database includes data such as the name or organization, contact person, date of meeting and comments related to experiences exchanged in the meeting.

8.1.2.5 Invite key actors to project meetings

Project meeting or events (virtual and in person) are good opportunities for inviting key actors (project leaders, researchers or stakeholders) to disseminate the objectives and advances in the project and try to establish synergies and common dissemination actions.

8.1.3 Clustering database

A clustering database has been created in order to achieve the objectives of the clustering strategy. Database is going to be completed with new organizations and projects during the whole project duration.

Key institutions and interesting related projects identified so far are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Key institutions and interesting related project identified for Clustering.

Organization	Meeting date	Projects	
EIT Raw Materials	16/11/2022	EuGeLi	https://eitrawmaterials.eu/project/eugeli/
		RIS-CuRE	RIS-CuRE: Zero waste recovery of copper tailings in the ESEE region - EIT RawMaterials
		BioLeach	BioLeach: Innovative Bio-treatment of RM - EIT RawMaterials
		INCO-Piles 2020	INCO-Piles-2020. International consortium to recover CRMs from stockpiles/tailings targeting RIS - EIT RawMaterials
EIT InnoEnergy	To be scheduled		
H2020 and Horizon Europe Projects			
FutuRaM	To be scheduled	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101058522	

8.2 KEY EVENTS AND MEETINGS

During this first period of the START project, the consortium members have participated in different events in which they have disseminated about the project, its main objectives and topics.

In these events, members have had the opportunity to seek connections with interesting stakeholders.

Main events that have described with more details in 7.1 are listed below:

- 1st scientific-technical conference of the geological and mining institute of Spain-National Center, Madrid (Spain) 12th-13th July 2022
- CEPAL Regional Event, Miraflores (Peru), 1st-4th Aug 2022: “Challenges for sustainable management of Mining Environmental Liabilities (MELs)”.
- PERUMIN 2022, Arequipa (Perú), 26th-30th Sep 2022
- International Workshop in Geochemistry, Medellín (Colombia), 19th-23rd Sep 2022
- World PM 2022, Lyon (France), 9th-13th Oct 2022
- EU-Latin America Raw Materials Convention and UE-Latin America Policy Dialogue on the identification of strategic and critical raw materials resources, Santiago de Chile (Chile), 2nd-4th Nov 2022
- Raw Materials Week, Brussels (Belgium), 14th-18th Nov 2022
- II Extraordinary General Assembly of ASGMI, Barcelona (Spain), 14th-18th Nov 2022

9 TASK 6.5: FINAL EVENT

Task leader: ASGMI; Participants: LNEG, All; M42 to M48

A final conference will be organised at the end of the project as a main dissemination event showcasing the successes achieved over the four years of the project.

The conference will likely take place in Brussels.

The details of the event (type of event, audience, keynote speakers...) will be determined during the project (starting around M42).

The final conference will try to be organised back-to-back with another mayor relevant event to ensure as large attendance as possible.

This task is not active yet. Nothing to report.

10 ANNEX I – START NEWSLETTER – ISSUE #1 – NOVEMBER 2022

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7377126

BIANNUAL NEWSLETTER OF THE START PROJECT | ISSUE 1

RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE

for a Sustainable Future

WELCOME FROM COORDINATOR

Filipe Neves (LNEG)

Dear members of the **START** community

Welcome to the first issue of the biannual Newsletter of the **START** project 'RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE for a Sustainable Future'. The objective of the Newsletter is not only to provide a summary of the activities and results of the project but also to address a variety of topics related to these activities, such as those related

with raw materials sustainability, sustainable energy ecosystems and business-innovation opportunities. The Newsletter is then organized in different sections, some of them will be repeated in every issue. For this first issue we have five sections: a first section dedicated to a general presentation of the **START** project where we invite you to meet our robot **STARTY** that, through a comic story, will introduce the project in an readily comprehensible way; a second section called '**START CHRONICLES**', with news on the project's activities; a third section of '**TECHNICAL PILLS**', where you will have the opportunity to read two short technical documents, one dedicated to Minerals sustainability and another on what are Thermoelectric materials; the fourth section is the '**CONSORTIUM TOUR**', in which we will introduce each of the **START** partners, and in this issue you will have the opportunity to learn more about LNEG and SINTEF; the fifth section is the '**CONTACTS**' area, where you can find how to get in touch with us and how to follow our social media accounts.

Let's now take a look to some important details of the **START** project. **START**, which stands for 'Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling', is an Innovation project, co-funded by the European Union and its Horizon Europe programme, with a budget of around 9.2 M€ and a duration of 48 months (started in June 2022). Our main objective is to build an innovation ecosystem in the EU related to the development of sustainable and economically viable tellurium-free thermoelectric waste heat harvesting systems. This will be achieved by producing advanced sulphide p-type semiconductor materials that will incorporate discarded mining waste sulphides (mainly consisting of the tetrahedrite-tennantite mineral series – see in the Technical Pills in this issue for definition), as valuable secondary raw materials and present in many European mine wastes, to replace the tellurium-based p-type materials.

So, what were the specific needs that triggered this project and the creation of this Consortium? Allow me to highlight 5 aspects:

1. The demand for a sustainable use of mine tailings to reduce the environmental footprint of mines and their waste piles and to increase the economic potential of such sites.
2. The necessity of an efficient use of the EU resources and security of raw materials by converting discarded waste secondary sulphide materials into useful and valuable secondary raw materials.
3. The need for recovering waste heat losses from industrial processes through thermoelectrics to promote a sustainable development for a decarbonised society.
4. The exigency of producing tellurium-free thermoelectric devices and based on alternative sustainable elements available in Europe.
5. The need to move towards a greener society and economy through eco-innovation and more sustainable economic models to promote energy security and encourage energy citizenship.

A multidisciplinary Consortium was then formed, comprising 15 partners from 10 EU member states and 1 associated country, including 6 research organizations with strong background and knowledge on geology, materials science, and renewable energies, 7 SMEs companies that guarantee the entire supply chain, from production, exploitation, and ecological footprint assessment, and 2 non-profit international associations with a consolidated network of partners and stakeholders.

In this context, and towards a more sustainable and resilient EU by building innovative value chains from raw materials to sustainable products, **START** proposes a unique technological solution based on the transformation of mining waste into materials for waste heat recovery, thus contributing to an efficient use of resources while promoting the use of green energy harvesting through thermoelectrics, in line with the strategies outlined in the European Green Deal and in the EU Action Plans on Critical Raw Materials and on Circular Economy.

As you can see, we are going to cover and address very interesting topics that are closely linked to today's societal challenges. The **START** Consortium thanks you in advance for your interest in the work that we will be developing, and of which you will also be an important part.

I hope you enjoy reading our first Newsletter and feel free to share it with anyone you think might be equally interested in these topics. Also, we are available for any further information, so please don't hesitate to contact us if you have any question.

Project: 101058632 HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01-07

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

STARTY EXPLAINS START

START CHRONICLES: START BEGINS AND PLANS BIG THINGS

LNEG HOSTED THE KICK-OFF MEETING

The official beginning of the **START** project occurred on 1st June 2022. On 20th-21st June, the Kick-Off Meeting was held in LNEG (**START**'s coordinator) premises in Lisbon, Portugal.

The meeting saw a large participation: 47 delegates from all 15 consortium partners were present, with the addition, on Monday, of the EU Project Officer Dr Marko Cacanowski, who could follow a thorough presentation about the project and its foreseen activities, results, and impact.

Following the main meeting, the first meetings of the General Assembly and of the Executive Committee also took place, and on 21st June a more operative meeting on the upcoming activities concluded the event. Some important decisions were taken and the activities of the first months were outlined.

The participants also enjoyed a consortium dinner on Monday night, that helped in making acquaintance with the other partners.

Here is a picture of the group that met in Lisbon, the first of a series of project General Assemblies!

Figure 1: Participants at the **START** Kick-off meeting in Lisbon

WORKPACKAGE 2: INITIAL WORK IN AUSTRIA, PORTUGAL AND SPAIN

The technical activities started during the summer months. In particular, we will be reporting here on Work Package 2, that is dedicated to 'Selection of mine waste sites; physical minerals separation and concentration'. The WP2 activity of the first months was linked to the Austrian cluster and to the Iberic cluster of partners.

In Austria, after literature research, two mine sites were selected (Nöckelberg and Schwaz) and a first sampling campaign of the two sites took place between August and September 2022, **Figure 2**. Samples have been prepared to be analysed for whole rock geochemistry, mineralogy and ore mineralogy.

Figure 2: Images taken in the mine wastes in Nöckelberg and Schwaz, in Austria

In Spain, the fieldwork was started in mid-September, in the Northwest, in the Asturoccidental Leonesa and the Asturian zones of the Iberian Massif. The provisional results suggest that the tailings with the greatest interest are those of the Segunda Cobriza mine, in Riello (León, **Figure 3**). There was also a visit to the La Estrella mine near Guadalajara, where interesting samples have been collected (see **Figure 4**).

In Portugal, a massive/stockwork sulphide mineralization sampling (700 kg of complex sulphide ore rich in tetrahedrite-tennantite) from the lower part of the Corvo (from the Neves-Corvo mine) ore bodies has been achieved with the support of the Lundin Mining Company (**Figure 5**). Sulphide samples are being analysed via mineralogical and metallogenetic studies.

Figure 3: Sampling at the Segunda Cobriza mine (Riello, Spain)

Figure 4: Sampling at the La Estrella mine (Guadalajara, Spain)

Figure 5: Sampling at the Neves-Corvo mine (Alentejo, Portugal)

START JOINS SEVERAL EVENTS IN EUROPE AND SOUTH AMERICA

Despite the fact that the start of the activities happened in June, However, the consortium is keen on disseminating about the project's concept and preliminary activities. Clearly, in this initial phase every dissemination is just to raise the awareness about the project and the topics linked to it, like recovering waste heat, thermoelectric materials and devices, reusing mine wastes to reduce materials dependence from third countries.

During the last weeks, many were already the events where **START** featured, one way or another, in Europe but also outside of Europe! Here is a short report for each of them.

1st Scientific-Technical Conference of the Geological and Mining Institute of Spain – National Center, Madrid (Spain), 12th-13th July 2022

E. Boixereu i Vila of IGME-CSIC presented the project at this event, that was hosted in the IGME headquarters in Tres Cantos, Madrid, Spain, in mid-July. This was done via a poster on show.

The proceedings of the event are available (<https://digital.csic.es/handle/10261/281251>) and www.zenodo.org/record/7092555#.Y2O5R-TMKHs, page 100).

CEPAL Regional Event, Miraflores (Peru), 1st-4th August 2022

The ASGMI Mining Environmental Liabilities Expert Group Chair, F Guzman, participated on the event organized by CEPAL (Comisión Económica para América Latina, or Economic Commission for Latin America, one of five regional commissions of the UN, based in Santiago de Chile – www.cepal.org/en/about) and named 'Challenges for sustainable management of Mining Environmental Liabilities (MELs)'.

The event took place in Miraflores, Peru from 1st-4th August 2022 (www.cepal.org/es/eventos/evento-regional-desafios-la-gestion-sostenible-pasivos-ambientales-mineros, in Spanish).

In his presentation 'Gestión sostenible de los Pasivos Ambientales Mineros: Enfoque en Iberoamérica', held on 1st August, F. Guzman showed a few slides about the **START** Project (general description and objectives) in which experts of the Group are going to participate as experts in sampling methodology.

Perumin 2022, Arequipa (Peru), 26th-30th September 2022

Perumin (www.perumin.com/perumin35/public/) is one the largest and most relevant mining conventions in Latin America (+60.000 participants, +1,400 stands and 29,000 m²). Its 2022 edition took place on 26th-30th September at the Cerro Juli Convention Center, located in the city of Arequipa (Peru).

Under the umbrella of the EC stand of the Mineral Development Network Platform and thanks to the link to the EU project 'EU-Latin America Partnership on Raw Materials' (www.mineralplatform.eu/about-the-platform/background), **START** was selected as relevant EU project and was promoted at the stand with a specifically generated banner. It was a key event for the promotion of **START** thanks to the enormous audience and being under the umbrella of the EC stand reinforced the project appeal.

START JOINS SEVERAL EVENTS IN EUROPE AND SOUTH AMERICA (Continued)

International Workshop in Geochemistry, Medellin (Colombia), 19th-23rd September 2022

The hybrid Workshop 'Geochemical Information for Society' (www.asgmi.org/taller-informacion-geoquimica-para-la-sociedad-19-23-septiembre-medellin/) organized by ASGMI and the Colombian Geological Service was held on 19th-23rd September 2022.

The objectives of the workshop were to present the manual of procedures and methodologies for taking and preparing geochemical samples, prepared by the ASGMI Group of Experts in Geochemistry -GEGEOQ-, to have an overview of the state of the art of geochemistry in Ibero-American countries and learn about the experiences of other Geochemistry Groups, such as those of IUGS, UNESCO and EuroGeoSurveys.

The **START** Project was briefly introduced by G. Olivenza (ASGMI) when talking about expert groups and projects.

World PM2022, Lyon (France), 9th-13th October 2022

World PM 2022 (www.worldpm2022.com) is a world event on Powder Metallurgy organized by EPMA: in fact, every 6 years the European Powder Metallurgy Association organizes the world congress, including both a congress and an exhibition. The event was hosted at the Congress Centre in Lyon (France), 9th-13th October: about 1100 participants both from industry and academia took part in the event, a significant figure given the fact the two previous editions (European congresses) had to be run online because of the pandemic, the last physical edition being the event Euro PM2019 in Maastricht (NL).

EPMA prepared a 3m x 3m booth for the project that was decorated with posters, roller banners, leaflets, a set of significant samples in a showcase with explicative labels, and a screen with a rolling video presenting the project for the whole duration of the exhibition. EPMA personnel covered the exhibition time as much as possible.

The coordinator Filipe Neves of LNEG was invited to give two presentations:

- Industry Corner: 30' presentation slot in the Exhibition area. Title: 'Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling' Speaker F. Neves. Tuesday 11th October 2022, 13:15-13:45.
- EuroFM Sectoral Group Meeting: Title 'The **START** project'. F. Neves was invited to present during the open meeting of the EPMA Sectoral Group on Functional Materials on Tuesday 11th October 2022, 17:00-18:30.

START JOINS SEVERAL EVENTS IN EUROPE AND SOUTH AMERICA (Continued)

The Technical Managers of EPMA, B. Vicenzi and K. Boz, mentioned **START** in all their presentations during the so-called Sectoral Group meetings (6 meetings and presentations overall).

Two other consortium companies were exhibiting in the event: Genicore and MBN.

The agenda is too large to be reported here but can be found at the following address: www.worldpm2022.com/technical-programme/. At page 69, an ad about **START** has been included in the technical guide.

As PM is one of the key technologies for **START**, participation was useful to raise the awareness in the PM community about these materials and application, and to start a networking activity for the project.

Geological Surveys from EU and Latin America together with key national and international organisations. The dialogue focused on the analysis of strategic and critical raw materials necessary for the clean energy and digital transition. The result of this dialogue will be a roadmap for the elaboration of the Critical and Strategic Raw Materials map in Latin America together with the Communication and Dissemination Strategy. The coordinator of the Mining Liabilities Expert Group, F. Guzman, participated in this physical meeting with a presentation of the group activities and also of the **START** project.

EU-Latin America RM Convention, and EU-Latin America policy dialogue on the identification of strategic and critical Raw Materials resources, Santiago de Chile, 2nd-4th November 2022

The 2022 EU-Latin America Convention on Raw Materials (www.mineralplatform.eu/events/eu-latin-america-convention-raw-materials-2022) took place on 3rd-4th November in Santiago, Chile and bringing together the mineral raw materials value chain community, including policymakers, industry, the private sector, and research and innovation actors, from the EU and Latin America under the following overarching theme: Mineral Raw Materials for the Clean Energy Transition. The Convention included a high-level (political) session on day 1, and panel sessions on days 1 and 2. On Friday 4th November, during the Panel session 'Downstream raw materials for the energy transition – refining, battery manufacturing & recycling', D. de Oliveira (LNEG) presented with the title '**START** project' the details of our project.

In connection with this convention, the 'EU-Latin America policy dialogue on the identification of strategic and critical Raw Materials resources' meeting took place (2nd-3rd November). This activity brings together

Raw Materials Week, Brussels (Belgium), 14th-18th November 2022

The seventh edition of the 'Raw Materials Week' took place from 14th-18th November 2022 as physical and hybrid, gathering a wide range of stakeholders discussing policies and initiatives in the field of raw materials. The programme included the ninth annual High-level Conference of the European Innovation Partnership (EIP) on raw materials and several complementary events on Critical Raw Materials, Trends in innovation and Skills for raw materials, EU-Ukraine Strategic Partnership on Raw Materials and batteries, EU Horizon technology success stories, EU-Canada Partnership, UNECE Resource management.

Some members of the consortium took part, with a good turnout in terms of networking, (200-300 attendees were present daily) and the introductory video and a poster of the project were shown on screen in the venue.

START JOINS SEVERAL EVENTS IN EUROPE AND SOUTH AMERICA (Continued)

Extraordinary General Assembly of ASGMI, Barcelona (Spain), 14th-18th November 2022

On 14th-18th November, the II Extraordinary General Assembly of ASGMI was held in Barcelona (Spain). Besides the Board of Directors meeting, an International Workshop was held on the topic 'The Role of Geological Surveys in the territorial planning and management', featuring the participation of the ASGMI Geological Surveys associated but also the participation of international organizations such as the EuroGeoSurveys, Geological Survey of Canada and United States, and the Organization of

Africans Geological Surveys. One of the presentations in the event, The Annual Report of Activities of the ASGMI Expert Groups, mentioned project **START** and showed the promotional video of the project.

Future events

START will surely take part in more events in the upcoming months. In particular, we are looking forward to the GENERA 2023 (international Energy and Environment Fair), that will take place in Madrid in February 2023.

We are also planning to run a free webinar, also around February 2023. The date, title and content have not been planned yet, so please check regularly for information on our website and social media, or even better, subscribe to our mailing list so that you will not miss any detail!

TECHNICAL PILLS

Some useful documents that cover topics that are linked to our project! We start with a document on raw materials issues in the EU and one on thermoelectric materials.

CRITICAL MINERALS AND RAW MATERIALS SUSTAINABILITY IN THE EU

Europe has the intention of becoming the world's first climate-neutral continent by 2050, meaning the implementation of the 'European Green Deal' by the European Commission (EC). Mineral resources are crucial to achieve this (green) transition.

Future projections indicate that resource demands could double between 2010 and 2030, mostly driven by demand in developing countries (European Commission, 2016) but also by green energy technologies, by the call for higher level of resource autonomy lately boosted by the energy price shock due to the Russian war against the Ukraine and the related embargo. The principal question is whether supply to meet these demands is adequate. Access to sustainable resources is a key for the EU's resilience in relation to raw materials. Achieving the much needed resources' security requires several actions to diversify supply from both primary and secondary sources, reduce the dependencies and to improve resource efficiency and circularity, including sustainable product design.

Mineral raw materials are crucial to the European economy. Non-energy mineral raw materials are linked to all industries in different key supply chains; technological progress relies on access to a growing number of raw materials.

Since 2011, the EU Commission has been concerned with the supply risk of these raw materials and has published triennial regular lists of Critical Raw Materials (CRM). The first list was published in 2011¹ with 14 materials, the

second in 2014², the third in 2017³ and the latest in 2020⁴ which now includes 30 CRM.

The two main parameters for determining criticality are economic importance (EI) and supply risk (SR) and are used to determine the criticality of the material for the EU. Critical Raw Materials are established on the basis of the raw materials which reach or exceed the thresholds for both parameters⁵. For the EU, CRM are those which display a high risk of supply shortage in the next ten years, and which are economically and strategically important for specific value chains. The mineral supply risk is linked to the concentration of production in a few non-European countries (e.g., USA (beryllium, helium), Brazil (niobium), DRC [cobalt], Rwanda [tantalum], South Africa [iridium, platinum, rhodium, ruthenium], Russia [palladium] and China (all CRM) (European Commission, 2018), and the low political-economic stability of some of the suppliers. This risk is compounded by low substitutability and low recycling rates¹.

The definition of a continuously updated list of CRM by the European Commission led to the first CRM Map of Europe in 2016. Following this, several countries have been surveying, preparing, and evaluating their mineral occurrences to create a resources/deposits database and, therefore, to create a CRM map of their own. With this purpose, LNEG created in 2021 the first Critical Raw Materials Deposit Map in Europe⁶.

CRITICAL MINERALS AND RAW MATERIALS SUSTAINABILITY IN THE EU (Continued)

A brief reference should be made to tellurium given its current relevance and weight in the production of thermoelectric materials. Tellurium is predominantly used in the production of cadmium telluride (CdTe) for thin-film solar cells. Another important end use is for the production of telluride-based materials (BiTe and PbTe), which are used in thermoelectric devices for both cooling and energy generation. About 30% of its global consumption by end use is for the production of thermoelectric materials⁷. Although not currently considered a CRM, tellurium is a relatively scarce element, with a terrestrial abundance of ca. 1 ppb and, at the same time, Europe is heavily dependent on imports, as China represents more than 60% of its production⁷. More than 90% of tellurium has been produced from anode slimes collected from electrolytic copper refining, and the remainder was derived from skimmings at lead refineries and from flue dusts and gases generated during the smelting of bismuth, copper, and lead-zinc ores. This fact represents a major drawback for the telluride-based thermoelectric technology, hampering its large-scale adoption in Europe.

Figure 6: Countries according to largest share of EU sourcing of CRMs⁴

Figure 7: Critical Raw materials deposits map in mainland Portugal⁶

WHAT IS A THERMOELECTRIC MATERIAL?

Thermoelectric (TE) materials are functional materials which have the ability of a direct conversion of thermal energy into electricity. Built into a TE device or a TE Generator these materials have attracted tremendous interests in the recent years, especially against the background of global energy shortage and surging of new materials.

When a TE device is loaded with a source of waste heat, for example in an industrial plant, a certain portion of this waste heat sources is converted in electricity, representing a direct saving of energy. Figure 8 provides a few examples from industrial waste heat, where huge amounts of high temperature energy is lost through radiation or in exhaust ducts.

The TE device is a robust and highly reliable solid-state energy converter with unique features: no moving parts, no maintenance, quiet operation, and absence of production of environmental deleterious waste. Due to this green behaviour, TE devices are expected to play a key role in clean and sustainable energy technologies.

TE materials work in a temperature gradient. Heat is the only input of a thermoelectric generator which produces electrical potential, or electricity if connected in a closed circuit. Heat can be generated either directly from the sun or the geothermal heat, or as a by-product of the consumption of fossil fuels.

Figure 8: Example of waste heat recovery from an industrial process via a TE generator (TEG)

WHAT IS A THERMOELECTRIC MATERIAL? (continued)

The maximum efficiency of a thermoelectric material is determined by its figure of merit,

$$zT = TS^2 \frac{\alpha}{\kappa}$$

where S is the Seebeck coefficient or thermopower, α the electrical conductivity, κ the thermal conductivity and T the absolute temperature. The best thermoelectrics are heavily doped semiconductors with high thermoelectric power factors ($S^2\alpha$) and low thermal conductivities, known as 'Phonon Glasses Electrical Crystals'. **Figure 9** depicts the dependence of the conversion efficiency dependent on the thermoelectric figure of merit zT, which is defined by the physical properties of the material as outlined above.

Figure 9: Dependence of conversion efficiency from zT and temperature difference

The tetrahedrite-tennantite series ($Cu_6[Cu_4(TM)_2](Sb,As)_4S_{13}$, with TM a transition metal), are p-type semiconductors with high Seebeck coefficient, and extremely low κ due to the complex cubic crystal structure. By adjusting the content of the doping element, competitive zT values, higher than 1, have been obtained between 300°C and 450°C, making tetrahedrites one of the bulk materials with the highest TE performance in this temperature range. **Figure 10** compares tetrahedrites with current commercial TE materials.

Materials	Current commercial materials			Tetrahedrite
	Bi_2Te_3	PbTe	SiGe	
Figure of merit (zT)	>1	>1	>1	>1
Operational temperature	< 300 °C	< 500 °C	< 900 °C	< 550 °C
Toxicity	■	■	■	■
Environmental aspects	■	■	■	■
Raw materials availability	■	■	■	■
Large scale manufacture	■	■	■	■

Favourable ■ Less favourable ■ Not favourable ■

Figure 10: Characteristics of commercially relevant thermoelectric materials and comparison with tetrahedrites

A scheme of a simple thermoelectric device is shown in **Figure 11**. Carriers (electrons in n-type material and holes in p-type) drift from the hot surface to the cold surface due to the higher average speed of the carriers in the hot surface. This builds an electrical potential across the materials which eventually counterbalance the drift. The proportionality of the created potential (ΔV) over the temperature gradient (ΔT) is defined as the thermopower of the Seebeck coefficient S. Real thermoelectric devices are built by connecting a certain amount of this p-n junction in series.

Figure 11: Scheme of a thermoelectric device: a temperature difference generates a difference of electric potential in coupled p-type and n-type thermoelectric materials

In a following Technical Pill we will see how to use this effect to build actual devices that can be used to harvest heat in practical environments.

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CONSORTIUM TOUR

We will introduce to you all consortium members, starting with the coordinator LNEG (Portugal) and the RTD partner SINTEF (Norway).

LNEG – NATIONAL LABORATORY OF ENERGY AND GEOLOGY

National Laboratory of Energy and Geology (LNEG) is a state laboratory that carries out advanced Research, Development, and Demonstration in the areas of Energy and Geology in Portugal, under the tutelage of the Ministry of Environment and Climate Action. LNEG actively participates in national and international projects and technological assistance and consultancy contracts with the business community, as well as providing support to public policies.

LNEG is scientifically organized into two laboratories: Laboratory of Energy (LEN) and Laboratory of Geology and Mines (LGM). LEN operates in the areas of renewable endogenous resources of energy and energy efficiency. It has the responsibility of knowing the potential of renewable energy resources and exploring innovative and strategic technologies to support the optimized use of resources with a view to decarbonization and the circular economy. LGM performs permanent functions of the State in the development of geoscientific knowledge of the emerged territory, the continental shelf and deep-water zones. It performs functions of National Geological Service. It is also responsible for the systematic geological survey of geological risks and resources, including resources in geothermal energy, geological storage, namely CO₂, and geological heritage.

The various international partnerships position the institution as a dynamic partner for internationalization and a source of privileged information in its areas of intervention. As an example, LNEG is a full member of international networks such as the European Energy Research Alliance (EERA), the European Sustainable Energy Innovation Alliance (ESEIA) and the EuroGeoSurveys (EGS). This is the context of LNEG's participation in European projects and its acceptance by international research entities.

LNEG promotes the implementation of Management Systems through standardization and continuous process improvement using tools to measure the efficiency and verify the effectiveness of actions. As such, LNEG hosts accredited laboratories within its structure, as a means to efficiently demonstrate the quality of the execution of the essays and in general, show technical competence. The set of laboratories accredited by the Portuguese Institute for Accreditation (in accordance with NP EN ISO 17025) includes the Laboratory of Biofuels and Biomass, which focuses its activity on the analytical methodologies for biofuels and solid and liquid fuels, Laboratory of Materials and Coatings, which is a centre specialized in the areas of characterization, corrosion / degradation and corrosion protection materials and the Laboratory of Solar Energy, which focuses on testing the Solar Thermal Collectors and Systems.

In addition, LNEG was awarded the certification NP4457:2007 for the Research, Development and Innovation Managing System for the activities in the fields of Energy and Geology, as well as the certification NP EN ISO9001:2015 of its Quality Management System for knowledge transfer activities in Energy and Geology. LNEG was the first institution in Portugal distinguished with 'Excellence in Human Resources Research' (HR Excellence in Research).

In **START**, LNEG is the coordinating institution of the project. LNEG is also responsible for the selection of mine waste sites; physical minerals separation and concentration work package, and it will be involved on research-based lab activities related with the mechanochemical synthesis production and materials characterisation. LNEG will also collaborate on the elaboration of the life cycle assessment task and will be responsible for the **START** serious game.

www.lneg.pt

SINTEF

SINTEF AS is an independent, not-for-profit research institute and part of the SINTEF Foundation. SINTEF is one of the largest independent research foundations in Europe, with about 2150 employees. The foundation earns the majority of its income from contract research for industry and the public sector in Norway as well as internationally. Contract research carried out by SINTEF ranges from basic through applied research to commercialisation of results in the engineering, physical and social sciences. SINTEF is represented in this consortium by the department of Sustainable Energy, with the Material Physics-Oslo (MFO) located in Oslo.

The MFO group has extensive expertise in materials characterization and modelling, using advanced electron microscopy/spectroscopy, mass spectrometry, surface topography techniques separate or in combination with atomic scale modelling based on quantum mechanics. The MFO group research activities lie mainly in materials for renewable energy, and in projects related to climate and environment. MFO is a central partner in the national infrastructures 'The Norwegian Transmission Electron

Microscopy Laboratory-NORTEM' and the 'National Surface and Interface Analysis Laboratory-NICE'. MFO owns and/or has access to advanced characterization instruments (www.sintef.no/en/all-laboratories/advanced-materials-characterisation-laboratory/) such as both state-of-the-art and modern workhorse TEMs (FEI Titan G2 60-300, JEOL ARM200F, JEOL 2100F, JEOL 2100, JEOL 2010), a FEG-SEM (FEI Nova NanoSEM 650), a FIB-SEM (FEI Helios Dual Beam FIB-SEM), three XPS spectrometers (2 KRATOS Axis-ULTRADLD, Thermo Fisher ThetaProbe), an AES/AEM Microprobe (JEOL JAMP-9500F FE), a ToF SIMS equipped with FIB (PHI nanoTOF), a WLI (Veeco Wyko NT-9800), various AFM, XRD, RAMAN, FT-IR instruments.

In **START**, SINTEF is responsible for the Materials Characterization work package and its state-of-the-art infrastructure with advanced characterization tools will enable to establish the structure and chemical behaviour of metal sulphides at the atomic scale, as well as their moelectric properties. SINTEF is also responsible for the materials modelling task and the device simulation task in **START**.

www.sintef.no

CONTACTS

START regularly updates its website and social media with news about its activities, but also with more general documents and info on the topics of relevance for the project. Thermoelectricity, waste heat recovery, mine waste reming, sustainability, raw materials and critical raw materials, energy efficiency, and many others.

If you are interested in receiving this newsletter and other special news from the project directly in your mailbox, consider subscribing our mailing list on the website ('Contacts' page, 'subscribe' section)! Clicking on the 'Subscribe' button, you will fill a form generated by SendinBlue, our mailing system, and will subsequently receive an E-Mail to confirm your address. Your data will be treated and stored in accordance with the EU GDPR Regulation. And do not forget to follow all our social media accounts!

Here is the list of the important links to click to reach our news:

Website: www.start-heproject.com

Twitter: [www.twitter.com/START_HEproject](https://twitter.com/START_HEproject)

LinkedIn: www.linkedin.com/company/86266991

YouTube: www.youtube.com/channel/UHVjEhpVz9uaEgzlCj2lnPA

SlideShare: <https://es.slideshare.net/StartProject/>

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